

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

Use Cases and Requirements Analysis 2

Work Package 2, Deliverable D2.3

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Use Cases and Requirements Analysis 2

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Lead:	Soomro, Kamran – UWE
Author(s):	Soomro, Kamran (UWE), UK Covato, Elisa, (UWE), UK Khan, Zaheer (UWE), UK Ludlow, David (UWE), UK Kirby, S. (Bristol City Council), UK Reeh, R. (Miljopunkt Amager), Denmark Vignoli, A., Bordi, C., Scavino, G. (I Borghi più belli d'Itali), Italy Martens, S. (BUAS), Netherlands

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List of Acronyms

CO	Citizen Observatory
DNSH	Do No Significant Harm
CoReS	Collaborative Requirements Engineering and Stakeholder engagement
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
PNRR	National Recovery and Resilience Plan

Glossary

Citizen Observatory	In GREENGAGE is a place like a <i>Living Lab</i> (a laboratory in a real context, putting stakeholders at the centre of the process) for collective learning that exploits the opportunity of using sensors and the use of Earth observation technology where citizens collect data and are empowered by the information generated from these data to improve environmental management towards an innovative governance of the territory.
Innovation Pilot	A small-scale experiment or trial of the GREENGAGE CO concept designed to test its feasibility, effectiveness, and potential impact. The goal of the innovation pilot is to validate the assumptions and hypotheses behind the GREENGAGE innovation, gather feedback and data, and identify any challenges or issues that need to be addressed before scaling up the innovation.
Use Case	In GREENGAGE, a use case is referred to as an instance of a task dealing with data handling (create, read, update, delete operations), described in a user-specific language without including technical and/or implementation details.
GREENGAGE Engine	The GREENGAGE Engine is the set of tools and software applications that make up the GREENGAGE toolset. They will be used to support the GREENGAGE COs in fulfilling the objectives of the Innovation Pilots.
Pilot Owner	The city or authority responsible for the implementation of a particular GREENGAGE innovation pilot.

Redmine	“Redmine is a flexible project management web application. Written using the Ruby on Rails framework, it is cross-platform and cross-database” https://www.redmine.org/ .
DNSH	Do No Significant Harm

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Executive summary

This report documents the finalised innovation pilot specifications for Bristol, Ørestad/Copenhagen, Gerace, Turano and North Brabant, their associated use cases and requirements for the GREENGAGE project. The Collaborative Requirements Engineering and Stakeholder engagement (CoReS) methodology has been adopted for this purpose. This methodology consists of several steps, namely; a) groundwork and context questionnaires, b) requirements gathering workshops, c) use case-based scenario requirements and d) requirements validation. Based on this methodology, several innovation pilot specifications were first developed, followed by use cases and requirements definition.

The pilot specifications have been developed to address the objectives of the European Green Deal within the context of the GREENGAGE project. These innovation pilots define the scope and context of Citizen Observatories (COs). As such a number of possible use cases and requirements have been derived from these pilot specifications that address various common challenges including citizens' mobility pattern analysis as well monitoring environmental conditions.

These use cases and requirements are an indication of what kind of experiments and data collection can be carried out in GREENGAGE pilots. The use cases and requirements have been validated by the innovation pilot representatives and reviewed by the technical partners, resulting in an acceptance or rejection of different requirements based on technical feasibility as well as relevance to the GREENGAGE objectives.

Overall, the innovation pilots demonstrate how COs can be used to promote sustainable and democratic solutions to policy challenges such as climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as healthy cities etc. In this regard, it is clear from the pilot specifications that **mobility is a major policy focus** that has particular relevance for the majority of innovation pilots and a central objective in delivering on the policy challenges identified above according to GREENGAGE objectives and the European Green Deal.

Related documents

GREENGAGE Deliverable D2.1 GREENGAGE CO Methodological framework

GREENGAGE Deliverable D2.2 Use cases and requirements analysis 1

GREENGAGE Deliverable D2.4 Smart governance models 1

GREENGAGE Deliverable D2.6 GREENGAGE technological requirements 1

GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aims to promote innovative governance processes, and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation and associated policies in the context of European Green Deal. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leverages citizens’ participation and equips citizens with innovative digital solutions that aim to transform citizen’s engagement and cities’ effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, the aim is to inspire citizens to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The objective is to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This will be facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories. In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories (COs) will facilitate innovation pilots in co-examining environmental issues, integrating novel bottom-up process with top-down perspectives. This will provide the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aims to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus¹, GEOSS², in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel decision-making methodologies and technologies.

As can be seen in Figure 1, the proposed citizens observatory campaigns will be deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Ørestad, Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano (Italy), Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, gathering new data which will complement existing datasets supporting evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of GREENGAGE.

¹ Copernicus - <https://www.copernicus.eu/en>

² GEOSS - <https://www.earthobservations.org/geoss.php>

Object of the Deliverable

This document outlines the activities and results of the Task 2.2 and Task 2.3 for REENGAGE, which involve defining the socio-economic and environmental use cases with public authorities and the analysis of stakeholder requirements and implied socio-technical challenges. This deliverable is an update of D2.2 - Use Cases and Requirements Analysis 1, which was due in M4. In D2.2 initial use cases and their requirements were analysed. In D2.3 the finalised use cases and requirements are presented and analysed. This task involves several project partners including UWE, AIT, DEUSTO, BUAS, KWMC, IBERCIVIS as well as Pilot Owners.

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1 Introduction

This report introduces innovation pilots and associated use cases and user requirements with the objective to highlight 'WHAT' is expected. The purpose of the innovation pilots is to identify scope and context of citizen observatories in Bristol, Copenhagen, Gerace, North Brabant and Turano. Furthermore, use cases and requirements aim to provide additional details for potential use cases which could be implemented using the GREENGAGE Engine. These use cases and requirements are co-created with pilot owners with the understanding that new use cases will be introduced by citizen observers during the piloting phase to support bottom-up problem identification and applying GREENGAGE solutions. These innovation pilots feed necessary information to WP3 for mapping the GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory Methodological Framework to GREENGAGE pilots' context, and preparing training material for the GREENGAGE CO Academy, knowledge base tool storage. Moreover, they highlight various possibilities to design and integrate GREENGAGE tools in WP4 to meet innovation pilots' needs using a flexible architecture that will handle emerging use cases and requirements (e.g., bespoke features) during the piloting phase.

The Collaborative Requirements Engineering and Stakeholder engagement (CoReS) method (Khan, Ludlow and Loibl, 2013) is applied to develop groundwork and context using questionnaires, followed by a requirements workshop involving pilot cities as well as technical partners. This workshop was co-located with the project "kick off" meeting, held in Bristol at the University of the West of England on 20th and 21st February 2023.

During this workshop in-depth discussions took place between the technical partners and the pilot cities. This was followed by detailed engagement with the cities, resulting in the specification of the innovation pilots. Subsequently, various use cases and requirements were derived from those pilot specifications. The results are documented in this report. These use cases and requirements are being validated and the latest version will be managed in the Redmine system to track changes and identify emerging requirements. The Redmine system will be used as the main source of up-to-date use cases and requirements throughout the project.

This deliverable is divided into two versions: Version 1 (due Month 4) and Version 2 (due Month 26). Version 1 outlined the initial activities and results of the pilot specification and requirements analysis process, while Version 2 reports use cases and requirements developed from co-creation with citizens and other community organisations. To address comments from the EC reviewers on version 1 of this deliverable, the following changes have been made:

1. The connection between GREENGAGE and the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood scheme was clarified in Section 4.1.1.
2. Ørestad stakeholders have been clarified in Section 4.2.3.
3. Use cases and requirements have been finalised in Section 6.

This deliverable is intended for innovation pilot representatives, technical tool developers, and product owners as it documents the innovation pilot specifications, use cases and requirements that will be implemented within this project. It is important to highlight that use cases and requirements development will be ongoing process due to both top-down and bottom-up CO nature of the GREENGAGE project. Therefore, a flexible and extendable GREENGAGE system architecture will be highly desirable to accommodate the emerging piloting needs.

2 Methodology

In any Information Technology (IT) project, requirements gathering, and management is an important aspect. Without requirements developers cannot understand user expectations and needs. Therefore, requirements must be properly managed and specified. For this purpose, we have adopted the CoReS methodology in the GREENGAGE project. This methodology was developed during the EC funded FP7 urbanAPI project and refined in subsequent projects. It has proved successful in fulfilling the aforementioned goals (Khan, Ludlow and Caceres, 2013). In GREENGAGE, the CoReS methodology consists of the following main components:

- 1) Groundwork and Context;

- 2) Requirements Gathering Workshop(s);
- 3) Innovation Pilot Specifications;
- 4) Use Case-Based Requirements;
- 5) Validation with Innovation Pilot Representatives and Technical Partners;
- 6) Requirements Management.

The overall process is coordinated and managed by a “Requirements Expert” role. The six CoReS components are selected for the following prime reasons:

- to understand the environment where Greengages’ digital solutions will be applied, with the objective to identify existing problems, stakeholders need, policy objectives and existing organisational processes;
- to understand stakeholders in order to develop user defined digital solutions by maintaining regular engagement with the stakeholders throughout the requirements development process;
- to gather, specify and validate digital solution requirements within specific timeframes without affecting other stages of the project development life cycle;
- to accommodate the needs and requirements of multiple stakeholders in various forms (i.e. pilot specifications, use cases, functional and non-functional requirements) with the objective to get better understanding of application requirements and to identify commonalities.

2.1 Groundwork and Context

The groundwork and context technique (Nuseibeh and Easterbrook, 2000; Finkelstein, 1993) is used to elicit basic requirements and establish an understanding of innovation pilot needs, in terms of policy goals, and constraints in order to establish the basis for effective participation in the requirements gathering workshops. In GREENGAGE, groundwork refers to the identification of innovation pilot goals, conflicts, scope of the system and boundaries, associated risks and alternative scenarios.

Similarly, context refers to the rationale for development, for example the extent to which the development of the COs is policy driven. To formally establish groundwork and context a questionnaire was prepared and distributed to innovation pilot representatives.

The questionnaire primarily addressed “WHAT” and “WHY” type questions, divided into general categories according to specific project needs. The questionnaire was distributed online and preliminary responses from all pilot owners were received prior to requirements workshop. The responses to the questionnaire assisted in structured requirement gathering and analysis. The questions were organised in the following categories (Full list of questions can be found in Annex A - Groundwork and Context Questionnaire):

Pilot Specification Questions

These questions focused on determining whether there have been any changes to the pilot specifications since the proposal (Description of Action - DoA) and understanding the nature of those changes. Furthermore, they focussed on understanding the policy context within which those pilot specifications should be understood and implemented.

Stakeholders and Users

This category of questions aimed to identify major stakeholders and their roles. Information obtained through these questions helped in stakeholder analysis for the GREENGAGE project. It is a similar approach as the well-known stakeholder mapping process.

Citizen Observatory/Citizen Science

These questions focused on understanding pilot cities’ prior experience with COs as well as the nature of the challenges with respect to CO implementations. Detailed guidelines on how to develop inclusive and ethically responsible citizen observatories are reported in Deliverable D2.1 GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework.

Data, Ethics and Privacy

This category of questions aimed to identify any data, ethics and privacy-related issues, e.g., any local laws that would impact how GREENGAGE is implemented in the various pilots.

Impact and Benefits

These questions focused on what impacts and benefits could be expected by applying GREENGAGE digital solutions to the innovation pilots.

GREENGAGE Technology Engine

This part of the questionnaire aimed to identify which GREENGAGE technologies (digital solutions) were relevant for each innovation pilot and how they could impact the needs of the pilots.

Smart Urban Governance Model

These questions meant to support understanding of the urban governance model within which the CO pilots will be implemented.

2.2 Requirements Gathering Workshops

The requirements gathering workshops were used as an instrument for face-to-face communication between GREENGAGE technology developers and innovation pilot stakeholders. The responses to the above questionnaire assisted in structured requirement gathering and discussions in the workshop. The objectives were to gather detailed requirements, based on direct discussion with the local pilot stakeholders, to acquire fuller understanding of local needs, policy issues and urban management goals. Furthermore, the identification of GREENGAGE innovation pilots, and associated data availability assisted in defining the feasibility of application development for specific pilots.

In GREENGAGE, prior to these workshops, introductory material for the GREENGAGE Engine was distributed to pilot stakeholders to allow them to become familiar with the GREENGAGE technologies. Participants to these workshops were mainly experts from different innovation pilots including urban planning, IT and GIS experts.

This process led to the identification of innovation pilot preferences for using GREENGAGE and also created the opportunity for discussions to clarify complex issues. For example, these discussions included identification of more specific user needs, restrictions on availability of mandatory data for applications, site identification to build pilot specifications, relevance to GREENGAGE objectives and other expected outcomes from GREENGAGE. The workshop was in hybrid mode (online and in-person) and there were over 35 participants. A full agenda of the workshop is included in Annex B, outlining the steps that were followed.

2.3 Innovation Pilot Specifications

Based on the requirements gathering workshops as well as the context and groundwork questionnaire and in further collaboration with the innovation pilot representatives, detailed specifications were derived. These specifications cover the background of the pilot, the legal, social and geographical context as well who are the main stakeholders and what is to be expected of the pilots. The pilot specifications are covered in Section 7.

2.4 Use Case-based Requirements

To secure a common requirements development approach and attract wider stakeholder participation, a use case-based requirements and design technique has been used. In the literature, use case-based requirements identification, analysis and design approaches are commonly used (Sutcliffe, n.d.; Kaindl, 2005; Whittle and Kruger, 2004; Sutcliffe *et al.*, 1998; Holbrook and H., 1990). The use cases were derived from the innovation pilot specifications which are also covered in Section 8 of this report.

In GREENGAGE, a use case is referred to as an instance of a task dealing with data handling (create, read, update, delete operations), described in a user-specific language without including technical and/or implementation details. A use case refers to a concrete narrative, or story, that describes the potential use i.e., one future possibility for a GREENGAGE technology offer. A use case may articulate

information including who uses the system, what are the users' roles and what are they trying to achieve – objectives and goals; what is needed in the application and why; the user-system interaction and the context in which the user will work with the system; the users' constraints and limitations; and clarifies what is regarded as a successful outcome of the application. This approach is useful to perform retrospective analysis and to derive, analyse and specify user requirements. Furthermore, it helps in presenting system specifications in user-specific terminology which can be more effectively validated by the end users. Multiple use cases were derived from each pilot specification.

2.5 Requirements Specification Template and Validation

In the CoReS method, a structured template is defined for requirements specification, and mainly used to elicit, analyse, specify and validate innovation pilot requirements. Each innovation pilot includes application-based stories, user needs and goals, specifies local stakeholders, and identifies functional and non-functional requirements. In GREENGAGE both use cases and requirements are derived and tracked separately.

Use cases have the following fields:

- 1) **Title:** The name or title of the use case.
- 2) **Description:** A brief overview of what the use case is about, what it entails, and what it is supposed to achieve.
- 3) **Priority:** The level of importance or urgency assigned to the use case relative to the other use cases.
- 4) **Status:** The current stage of the use case development process, such as Under review, Awaiting Feedback, Rejected or Accepted.
- 5) **Use case owner:** The innovation pilots to which the use case belongs.
- 6) **Rationale:** The reason why the use case is important, what problem it is meant to solve, and how it will benefit the system or organization.
- 7) **Pre-conditions:** The conditions that must be met before the use case can be executed, such as what datasets should be available.
- 8) **Post-conditions:** The state of the system or environment after the use case has been executed successfully.
- 9) **Potential technologies:** The GREENGAGE technologies or tools that could be used to implement the use case, such as MODE or UrbanTEP.

Requirements have the following fields:

- 1) **Requirement:** A brief statement of the requirement.
- 2) **Description:** A brief explanation of the requirement, which should provide enough information to understand what the requirement is and why it's needed.
- 3) **Associated Use Case:** Other use case(s) to which the requirement is linked.
- 4) **Priority:** The level of importance of the requirement, such as high, normal, or low.
- 5) **Status:** The current state of the requirement, same as use case.
- 6) **Innovation Pilot Owners:** Those responsible for the requirement.

In GREENGAGE the Redmine tool is used to manage the use cases and requirements. At the time of writing this report the Redmine set up was not ready and so Sharepoint lists were used for developing requirements. Each use case and requirement contain the above fields. The requirements are linked to the use cases that they are derived from for traceability purposes. Representatives of each innovation pilot were asked to validate the requirements and provide additional details if necessary. At the time of writing the requirements validation by the innovation pilots is still underway.

3 Stakeholder Analysis

All GREENGAGE pilots identify a wide range of stakeholder communities that have interest and involvement in the development of the GREENGAGE pilots and the enhancement of the planning decision-making process and governance model deploying COs. This multiplicity of stakeholders and diversity of roles in relation to the project pilots strongly influences and defines their requirements and expectations from the project which are also diverse.

Broadly stakeholders can be categorized in terms of a 3-fold division of the interests and engagement:

- **Public institutions:** local authorities (municipalities, provinces, regions, etc.), functional agencies (consortia, chambers of commerce, health agencies, environmental agencies, research centres, etc.); e.g., **East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood** - Cabinet members, ward members; **North Brabant** - Province of North Brabant.
- **Organised groups:** pressure groups (trade associations, political parties and movements, mass media), local associations (cultural, environmental, consumer, social associations, sports or recreational groups, etc.); **Gerace** - Citizens Observatory for Urban Regeneration; **North Brabant** - SmartwayZ reizigerspanel, Ov-reizigerspanel, KBO-Brabant and Technology companies such as Argaleo and Mobidot; **East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood** - Sustrans and Bristol Walking Alliance.
- **Unorganised groups:** citizens and communities (all citizens making up the local community) represented in all Innovation Pilots.

In this context a further distinction and differentiation commonly applied to the analysis of stakeholder communities concerns the division between stakeholders and end users. Stakeholders and end-user communities are both groups of people that can influence the development of a product, service, or organization. However, there are some key differences between these two groups:

- **Stakeholders** are individuals or groups that have an interest or stake in an organization, project, or decision. They can be involved in the decision-making process, providing feedback, and making suggestions to ensure that their interests are considered. Nonetheless, the goals of stakeholders may not always align with the goals of the organization, and conflicts can arise if their needs are not taken into account.
- **End-user** communities are groups of people who use a particular product or service, and end-user communities are best placed to provide feedback on the development of the proposed solution. At the same time the goals of end-user communities are usually aligned with the goals of the organization, as they want a product or service that meets their needs and expectations.

The interactions between the various stakeholders identified in the 3-fold division specified above, and their identities as end users or stakeholders in the context of GREENGAGE pilots drives the development of the GREENGAGE governance planning model (refer to Deliverable D2.4 Smart Governance Models 1) and is critical to the specification of their roles, requirements and expectations in the project. Critically in this governance project end-user activities are identified with the public institutions including a range of both political and professional actors involved in planning decision-making process and who are seeking clear enhancement of the decision-making process by the deployment of CO derived technology applications. As such these groups and their requirements and expectations are paramount to the specification of the technology supported engagement in bottom-up governance process as delivered via COs.

Nonetheless GREENGAGE objectives also include the promotion of the engagement of citizens and non-government organizations in the planning governance process, and consequently the requirements and expectations of these groups (organised and unorganized) also form an important consideration in the design development and delivery of the GREENGAGE pilots.

4 GREENGAGE Innovation Pilots

4.1 Bristol Innovation Pilot

4.1.1 Background and Context

The East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood pilot (Figure 2) is in the inner east of Bristol with geographical coverage 1.7 km². It has approximately 6000 properties and businesses within the area. Bristol has stated the ambition of becoming Carbon Neutral by 2030.

Figure 2: Liveable neighbourhood project area.

Liveable Neighbourhoods are areas of a city where improvements are designed in partnership with local communities to achieve a better balance between how streets are used for vehicles and people.

In June 2021 Bristol's Citizens' Assembly called for our neighbourhoods to be reimagined so that they are people-centred and more 'liveable', meaning they are safe, healthy, inclusive, and attractive places where everyone can breathe clean air, have access to better quality green and public space, and feel a part of a community.

Rolling out two Liveable Neighbourhood pilot projects are Mayoral priorities for Bristol, with the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN) being the first scheme to be piloted in the city.

A strategic walking and cycling route, the Wesley Way, in east Bristol was identified along Beaufort Road through St George, Redfield and Barton Hill (Bristol/South Gloucester Route 3) in the Local Cycling and Walking Infrastructure Plan (LCWIP).

The West of England Combined Authority (WECA) has provided funding to use an area-wide approach to develop a Low Traffic Neighbourhood (Liveable Neighbourhood), rather than just design linear infrastructure for route improvements. The project area covers parts of five wards of Bristol: Lawrence Hill, Easton, St George West, St George Central and St George Troopers Hill, south of Church Road and north of the River Avon.

Liveable Neighbourhoods have been controversial in some areas of the country where they have been introduced rapidly. Therefore, it is vital for this project to be community led, with meaningful engagement at every stage in the process.

Keeping the above points in mind, the EBLN scheme is being implemented in various stages by the Bristol City Council. These include:

1. **Co-Discover:** In this phase intelligence gathering was conducted to determine the demand for a liveable neighbourhood within citizens in the area.
2. **Co-Design:** In this phase the Bristol City Council engaged with the citizens via meetings and street events to develop plans for a trial scheme.
3. **Trial scheme:** This is the next phase of the project currently underway. Temporary measures are being implemented to redirect the flow of traffic through the pilot area to promote active

travel. The installation of temporary measures was expected to finish by the end of January. However, heavy resistance by some residents has caused significant delays in the progress of the trial phase.

REENGAGE will play an important role during the current trial phase for monitoring and to provide useful insights based on which permanent interventions can be applied in phase 2 of the EBLN project. It is expected that during the trial phase two REENGAGE Observatories (GOs) will be implemented that will provide an opportunity for REENGAGE to help monitor the scheme and collect evidence for further decision-making.

4.1.2 Goals and Objectives

Our vision for the Liveable Neighbourhood programme is to empower local communities to transform their neighbourhoods into places which provide better access to green and play space, more seamless and convenient connections to local amenities using sustainable forms of travel, and more space for social and community activity.

The objectives of Liveable Neighbourhood programme are to:

- Improve local and citywide air quality and contribute to meeting the climate and ecological emergency.
- Improve residents' physical and mental health and wellbeing.
- Improve levels of physical and perceived safety in our communities.
- Contribute to reducing inequality and opening opportunities for all in our communities.
- Improve local accessibility and connectivity to shops, schools, services, and other amenities for everyone to move around safely and sustainably.
- Transform our neighbourhoods to places where people want to spend time, can interact with neighbours, and enjoy their unique identities.
- Reflect the needs and characteristics of the local community and increase the sense of pride and belonging.

4.1.3 Pilot Specification

The pilot project has utilised a co-design approach seeking feedback and input from the local community to help design a re-imagined streetscape that realises the vision set through the Citizen Assembly.

The first round of engagement, "Co-Discover" sought to understand what people loved about where they lived, and what they would like to change to make it even better. The community were invited to map the issues and opportunities through both in person and online events. The results of the Co-Discover phase of engagement are summarised [here](#).

The results of the Co-Discover phase helped set the priorities of the community and enabled the team to create several design tools that could help provide solutions to the issues raised. A [design toolkit](#) was published in advance of the second round of engagement, "Co-Develop".

The Co-Develop phase of engagement sought to understand and map, where and what measures, the community would like to see on their streets. Interactive workshops were hosted in person and online, where the design team would provide support and technical advice on what people would like to see on their streets. Innovative [engagement tools](#) developed by the Alan Turing Institute were used during the workshops to help the community develop a holistic design for the transport measures required to deliver quieter streets.

The outputs from the Co-Develop phase have been used to inform the development of a holistic scheme that addresses the needs of the community. The results of the Co-Develop phase of engagement are summarised [here](#).

This scheme will be implemented on a trial basis to understand how the scheme works, whether it achieves the aims and what improvements may be required.

Figure 3: Bristol pilot trial scheme

The pilot now seeks to implement the phase 1 scheme as a trial (shown in Figure 3), following the submission of an Outline Business Case to the funding body, WECA. This will be delivered using temporary materials and will remain in place for 6-18 months whilst further engagement is undertaken with the community to determine how the scheme could look if made permanent. The phase 2 scheme will deliver elements of the project that can only be constructed in a permanent way such as, new crossings and junction upgrades.

The pilot project will collect data throughout the trial scheme to determine whether the scheme is a success. GREENGAGE technologies will be deployed with citizen scientists to fill the 'data gap' that is often experienced with transport schemes. By directly involving the community in the data collection, monitoring and evaluation of the trial, the pilot project can build community trust with the Council and create greater transparency for decision making on how the scheme could become permanent.

The pilot project will involve a multidisciplinary team of experts, including data scientists, software developers, transportation planners, and community engagement specialists, to ensure a participatory and user-centred approach. The pilot will also provide tools to citizens to define other experiments and make use of pilot and auxiliary open data to solve problems deemed more relevant to the pilot community. These insights can provide useful insights to public administration for interventions and/or policy making.

The pilot project will be evaluated based on its ability to collect high-quality and representative data, generate useful insights and recommendations, and engage citizens in the project.

4.1.4 Stakeholders

The stakeholders in the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood Pilot include:

- 1) Public institutions:
 - a. Council cabinet members
 - b. Bristol ward members
 - c. Members of Parliament
 - d. Bristol City Council internal project teams

- 2) Organised groups:
 - a. Bristol One City Transport Board (such as Sustrans and Bristol Walking Alliance)
 - b. Accessibility and equality groups (such as Bristol Physical Access Chain or Older Peoples' Forum, Green and Black Ambassadors and Black Seeds Environmental Social Justice Network)
- 3) Unorganised groups:
 - a. Community champions (such as paid professionals, community animators and connectors from local organisations as well as active residents)
 - b. People who live in the area, or just outside the area
 - c. People who travel to or through the area
 - d. Local businesses, shops and local services (such as waste collection)
 - e. Local schools and other educational establishments

4.1.5 Pilot pre-conditions

GREENGAGE Engine must be linked with the existing [Liveable Neighbourhood platform](#) from where communication and co-creation and co-design activities are on-going.

4.1.6 Pilot post-conditions

Analysis tools and insights are accessible to public administration for interventions and/or policy making, as well as to citizens to define other potential experiments and solutions.

4.1.7 Use Cases

Table 1 lists the use cases that have been finalised for Bristol. Several use cases were rejected that have not been included here. Details requirements are shown in Table 9 and Table 10.

Table 1: Use cases finalised for Bristol. IDs are auto generated by Planio.

#	Priority	Subject	Description
536	Normal	Mobility pattern analysis to determine accessibility to shops, schools, services and other local amenities	Use techniques such as app-based location or GPS tracking to determine routes that citizens take to local amenities and identify improvements. Categorise routes by mode of transport and analyse alternative travel modes.

535	High	Monitor environment and automatically identify safety / threat levels	<p>Identify and analyse threat levels of various neighbourhoods or streets and visualise for further analyses and input to policymaking.</p> <p>Analyse threat levels of various neighbourhoods and visualise for further analyses and input to policy-making. Threat could come from: A) cars / traffic B) environmental pollution C) public realm concerns D) bike theft</p> <p>Things to consider are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - poor lighting - road crossing - vehicle speed - inconsiderate or illegal parking - driver/cycling behaviour - crimes (anti-social behaviour etc.) - littering - accessibility such level surfacing for people with disabilities - children height and vehicles parked can be a cause of hazard - underutilised or less surveillance routes - etc. <p>Use technical solutions for automated detection by using GREENGAGE ENGINE. We are not after surveys with general public.</p> <p>In addition, street safety/health index metrics may be used to autodetect some of the things such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Motorised vehicle speed Volume of motorised traffic Mix of vehicles Cycle safety at junctions Ease of crossing side roads Ease of crossing between junctions Priority of crossing at junctions Navigation of crossings for people with visual impairments Space for walking Quality of the carriageway surface Space for cycling Lighting Reducing convenience of driving short journeys
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533	High	Analyse and visualise impact of road closures on mobility patterns (journey quality)	<p>The system will use historical mobility and road closure data and analyse mobility patterns before and after road closures. It will also compare traffic flow, travel times, and congestion levels before and after road closures and identify any significant changes in mobility patterns and potential causes. It will visualise and report the results to stakeholders and decision-makers.</p> <p>Possible steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User opens visualisation tool. • User loads data for visualisation. • User selects analysis mode (mobility patterns, traffic flow, congestion levels etc). • User downloads/exports analysis information (png, spreadsheets etc).
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4.2 Ørestad, Copenhagen Innovation Pilot

4.2.1 Background and Context

The Notion of a neighbourhood connects to two definitive aspects that connects in the identity of the place: First, it is a geographically distinction - a neighbourhood is by definition a subset of a larger city. Secondly, it refers to a community of the people in the area.

Ørestad (as depicted in Figure 4) is selected as pilot demonstration site. It is a distinct neighbourhood in Copenhagen. It is located to the southwest of the city centre on the island of Amager, along the nature reserve of the 'Common'. It is a mix residential, commercial, and university (Law, Humanities, and IT University) buildings, with approx. 25.000 people in each sector.

Ørestad lies within the district of Amager Vest. An elected local council has local authority, including the mandate to drive the environmental and climate forward. Local Council of Amager Vest delegates (together with the Local Council of Amager East) this responsibility to Miljøpunkt Amager.

Ørestad qualifies as a neighbourhood on both accounts. Born out of Municipality of Copenhagen financial austerity in 1990s, a strip of land from the nature reserve of 'the Common' was sold off as a brown field development to private developers to soothe city coffers. Since then, more brown fields have been erected in Copenhagen, but Ørestad was very much the first. This is reflected in about every aspect of life in Ørestad from every cornerstone to the residents' shared pioneering mentality.

Figure 4: The area of Ørestad in Copenhagen

The Legacy of Transport Oriented Development

The intentions were to build a new district for modern living with easy access to the city centre, motorway and the airport just nearby. Concerted efforts installed universities and commercial headquarter to accelerate the inhabitation of the neighbourhood. Infrastructure was built in support: Copenhagen-Kastrup Airport (CPH)'s first metro line ends here, so was a new bridge to Sweden, and the airport was expanded; Regional trains, metro and the new motorway connects at the centre of Ørestad, splitting the neighbourhood in two.

The human aspects of quality of living in the neighbourhood, however, were much overlooked in the process: Human scale have given way to broad, straight boulevards where the metro runs overground centre throughout the neighbourhood; at street level the buildings do not open up to the streets leaving few places for urban life. The micro-climate is in most places unpleasant as tall, solitary buildings drag the turbulent, coastal wind to the streets.

The Transport Oriented Development paradigm creates in Ørestad several environmental hazards, especially air, noise and moving light pollution. Each of these are documented to bring severe and fatal health hazards to humans. Figure 5 (level of noise) and Figure 6 (ultrafine particles) depict some of these issues.

Figure 5: Ørestad is located between major transport related sources of noise, namely airport, regional trains, the metro-line, and the motorway. Ørestad noise map (Blue is above 75 dB, yellow marks the regulatory limit of 55 dB. Source: Danish Environmental Agency)

Figure 6: Ultrafine particles in Copenhagen neighbourhoods. Source Google and University of Utrecht, 2021

Supporting the City and the Neighbourhood’s effort to become green, healthy, and sustainable

Every city is struggling to transform cities to become in line with planetary boundaries. In Copenhagen Deputy Mayor, Line Barfod, has called for a shared effort to find new ways to solve the climate challenge that runs across segments in the cities. This is an open-ended task where all groups are invited. It is also of vast magnitude where all kinds of intelligence are needed.

Ørestad reflects many of the ‘roles’ that cities posit. It is a regional economic centre with a high influx of commuters to the area. It is a residential area with segments at different stages of life; It is an area with many students passing through the neighbourhood. As such, it is a micro cosmos of urban dynamics - as a Citizen Observatory it provides an opportunity to give a general input to policy that can be adapted in a wider setting.

The Greengage Citizen Observatory provides an opportunity to utilise the citizen-centric perspective and work across silos. From a citizen perspective e.g., little coordination exists between urban planning and the interface to transport systems - the areas around train stations are not planned as part of a commuter journey but only as a local hub for other means of transport, mainly busses.

The Citizen Observatory strives to reflect the needs of the wider local community. In local democratic community processes, it is often a challenge to have all segments participating in the processes, due a variety of reasons. One is time constraints as citizens are caught between work and family obligations. It is part of the Greengage Citizen Observatory in Copenhagen to investigate how digital solutions can be added to local democratic processes.

Data collection will be an important part of this investigation and in supporting local democratic dialogue and decision process. Data collection will be carried out by residents and commuters - to support the

dialogue the Citizen Observatory in Copenhagen will establish a feedback loop where initial results will be published to engage and to provide citizens an opportunity to reflect and comment.

4.2.2 Goals and Objectives

The Greengage Citizen Observatory in Copenhagen will start from the political call to action to find new solutions and alternatives to fossil-based socio-economic and environmental functioning of cities. Since cities are complex systems with multiple stakeholders and interests, solutions need to take account the plethora of perspectives from residents, companies, commuters etc. into a democratic process.

The Ørestad use cases have been selected to build on top of previous and existing efforts in the neighbourhood. The efforts have followed a two-pronged approach; one that is trying to reverse the physical structures that hinders improving quality of life. The most ambitious attempt is to have the motorway covered to combat noise and air pollution, but also smaller scale initiatives to seek out spaces for a greening of the urban environment. The second evolves around transforming the area into a resilient people-centred area. Several initiatives have tried to identify citizens' needs without solid take up from decision makers. These efforts receive interest from local companies and consensus is building to work to be sizeable living lab for a climate positive neighbourhood.

The overall vision for the Greengage Citizen Observatory in Copenhagen is to align urban spaces with planetary boundaries while improving conditions for urban living. This includes to transform the neighbourhood with more places where people enjoy spending time and interacting with neighbours.

Objective 1: To test and investigate if citizen science and crowdsourced data collection can be utilised positively to engage citizens in local democratic dialogues in the pursuit of new solutions towards creating a climate-positive neighbourhood.

Objective 2: To use data collection to illuminate the existing lived experience and conditions in the neighbourhood as a baseline for generating citizens' ideas to where to improve the urban layout.

Objective 3: To use new digital solutions of data collection to understand citizens' needs for mobility, including local mobility, commuting mobility and access to the city in wider perspectives, and how integration into city planning processes can improve conditions.

The three objectives will be carried out by following these steps:

Prepare the project - identify key stakeholders who will and can lead the vision for the neighbourhood forward.

Establish a baseline - utilising access to cutting edge technologies the Greengage project will establish a baseline collected by citizens to document existing living and environmental conditions in a manner where data are trustworthy and verifiable.

Enable a shared dialogue - feedback loop to the neighbourhood on data and findings that is recognised by main stakeholders. From 'shared dialogue' actions are determined - prioritises key actions to follow and monitor.

Plan the implementation - work to secure financing and political mandate for delivering long-term outcome.

4.2.3 Stakeholders

During the implementation of the GREENGAGE pilots, the following stakeholders have been identified:

- **The Local Council of Amager Vest:** one of 12 local councils in Copenhagen. As a democratic institution and part of the Municipality of Copenhagen, it comprises 25 elected members of which 15 are elected from local organisations, and 10 candidates from political parties. Local councils have responsibilities for local planning, citizen dialogues and public hearings, distributes finance to local initiatives.
- **Municipality of Copenhagen:** In the GREENGAGE project several departments and offices are included in the process: Deputy Mayor Line Barfoed and office hold quarterly meetings with Miljøpunkter; Department of Mobility and Traffic, Office for Citizen Engagement, Office for Neighbourhood Refurbishments (Amagar), plus support from the Office of City Data.

- **Ørestad Innovation, OICC:** a local innovation facilitator. Members are local businesses, universities and finance institutions to support Ørestad as a hub for innovation and innovative companies.
- **GFS:** an umbrella organisation for building owners in Amager Vest. Maintains large parts of private areas and serves as a coordinator for new initiatives.

4.2.4 Pilot Pre-Conditions

Existing data from recognised data sources, e.g. EU satellite data, shall be used together with any new collected data, to avoid unnecessary data collections. Algorithms and analytical processes used should be transparent and within EU legislation.

4.2.5 Pilot Post-Conditions

All anonymised data, and results produced in the project should be open and accessible to citizens under Creative Commons licensing.

4.2.6 Use Cases

Table 2 lists the use cases finalised for Ørestad, Copenhagen. Detailed requirements are listed in Table 11 and Table 12.

Table 2: List of use cases finalised for Ørestad, Copenhagen. IDs are auto generated by Planio.

#	Priority	Subject	Description
577	High	Mobility pattern analysis to determine accessibility to shops, schools, services and other local amenities	Use techniques such as app-based location or GPS tracking to determine routes that citizens take to local amenities and identify improvements. Categorise routes by mode of transport and analyse alternative travel modes.
576	High	Participatory environmental monitoring	Monitor environmental data such as air quality, noise levels. Citizens would capture such data using portable sensors; then analyse and visualise them using a shared platform to identify sustainable improvements.
575	Normal	Air quality monitoring	<p>Monitor and visualise air quality pollutant levels in the neighbourhood at different times (e.g. at different times of the day, for different congestion levels etc).</p> <p>From Copenhagen Pilot specifications:</p> <p>> Exposure to air pollution has many consequences for people. For companies this means lower productivity and more sick leave, commuters are highly exposed on motorways, and residents live shorter. All parties gain from changing their exposure patterns. Data will be used to engage all parties in a dialogue on how solutions can benefit all. Orestad is one of the areas in Copenhagen with the highest levels of air pollution. Human exposure includes residents, employers and commuters to the headquarters adjacent to the motorway. An earlier project has revealed first impressions that existing modelling underestimates levels in places where microclimate conditions are pleasant (from shelter from the wind). The investigation will collect air quality data using a number of different sensors, including stationary sensors and mobile sensors to record exposure to humans during transport and recreation. This part of the project will be assisted</p>

			by epidemiologists from Utrecht University and the University of Copenhagen. The scientists will also be a resource for the communication and dissemination of results and health consequences
537	High	Analyse citizens' usage of public spaces and determine attractiveness of public spaces.	<p>Use GPS data, or other techniques, and analyse the usage profile of public spaces (parks, shops, etc). Identify spaces that are the most used and the least used during different times of the day. This analysis feeds into the local traffic plan.</p> <p>From the Copenhagen pilot objective (Objective2 - Urban life)</p> <p>> The objective is to set a baseline for the social life of the neighbourhood, i.e. create an overview of the current use of the urban spaces in the neighbourhood, i.e. where, why, and by whom. The objective shall be able to support neighbourhood planning and democratic dialogue for all segments. It is expected that mobile camera technologies can form a unified registration and count of where people are. It is also expected that more anthropological methods will be applied to understand segmented motivations, preferences, alternatives etc. The task will be assisted by University of Copenhagen, Cultural Studies.</p>

4.3 North Brabant Innovation Pilot

4.3.1 Background and Context

The Province of North Brabant is in the South of the Netherlands with geographical coverage 5,081km² housing about 2.5 million citizens. Due to its job and education opportunities, and appealing natural environment, the province is rapidly growing, which comes with challenges. Chief amongst which is a rapid urbanisation, creating a demand for 12.000 dwellings in liveable and sustainable neighbourhoods per year. To tackle this and associated traffic safety, health, inclusivity, economic and energy challenges the province of North Brabant envisions a transition to sustainable traffic and transport as a key pursuit (Provincie Noord-Brabant *et al.*, 2022). The policy aims at 20% more cycled kilometres by 2027 and 40% by 2040, achieved through stimulation of biking, but primarily through the provision of more space to use the bike in everyday movements, recreation, commute, and multimodal traffic.

Although the province already has a strong urban and even regional bike infrastructure (bicycle highways), the choice to shift to sustainable transport requires more than physical means. Some regional movements are too long for bike travel, so motorized vehicular travel plays a dominant role in the mobility of Brabant as well, with about 80% of the trips longer than 6km made by car (Provincie Noord-Brabant, 2020). The shift to sustainable transport has not occurred to its full capacity.

The goal of this pilot project is to generate knowledge on how to achieve a higher shift to sustainable transport, and that requires understanding why the car is still the most chosen modality, and what elements of the choice for bike travel can be strengthened to increase the appeal of that option. For this, citizens need to be engaged in the reflection on their choices as well as their travel patterns, and in the targeted identification of obstacles to the use of the bike. Having a better idea of how and why people choose to travel a certain distance with by bike or by car or other modes allows for the co-creation of optimal conditions for sustainable travel for as many people as possible in neighbourhoods and regional connections.

A citizen observatory for sustainable traffic and transport is part of a large-scale GPS data collection scheme that outlines citizens origins and destinations, travel mode choices and route choices and overall indicators for network quality (e.g., delays and detours). Next to this quantitative data gathering, the experiences and decisions of the citizens offer qualitative data on possible apprehensions to

switching from car to sustainable transport. Involving citizens in the gathering and signification of this data can strengthen the policy agenda through a more grounded understanding of obstacles to sustainable travel, and the decision process that precedes it. While focusing on giving more space to bike travel, this engagement can ultimately reflect on the liveability and sustainability of North Brabant.

4.3.2 Goals and Objectives

The goal of this pilot project is to generate knowledge on how to achieve a higher shift to sustainable transport, specifically from car to bike. To increase that understanding, this pilot will collect and analyse different types of qualitative and quantitative data through citizen observatories. The specific objectives of the pilot project are:

- 1) To establish citizen observatories that can collect, validate, and interpret qualitative and quantitative data, and are structurally integrated into a dialogical approach to governance discussing the liveability and sustainability of Brabant;
- 2) The collection and validation of a range of quantitative data (e.g. origin-destination and routing data on the urban-regional connection) and qualitative data (e.g. the process of decision making in modality choices) by citizens through a variety of data gathering methods (e.g. a mobile GPS tracking app) and the analysis of this data within a digital twin to assess neighbourhood liveability and sustainability;
- 3) To include women and historically marginalized groups such as ethnic minorities, disadvantaged populations and disabled persons in the gathering and signification to ensure an inclusive perspective on the assessment of liveability and sustainability;
- 4) To aggregate the mobility data into a digital twin to strengthen its use as an evidence-based decision support tool;
- 5) To experiment with a 3-layer approach within the digital twin to facilitate policy making, looking at the combination of macro (e.g., GPS, Satellite, land use data), meso (e.g., mobility and spatial data from transport companies, traffic organisations, and policy indicators), and micro (citizen gathered data on, for instance, mobility routes or decision processes) data;
- 6) To generate additional knowledge on the process of shifting to sustainable transport through different qualitative and quantitative data analyses (e.g., why is the car still used when efficient and effective bike highways exist) and on involving citizens more intensely in governance through co-creation.
- 7) To use the data and citizen engagement to improve the conditions for sustainable transport on, for instance, spatial, environmental, and community level;
- 8) To set up more targeted campaigns to remove obstacles for biking in the decision process.

4.3.3 Pilot Specification

The pilot project targets the mobility transition throughout the whole province (shown in Figure 7). A possible starting point of the pilot can be the Brainport region - the city of Eindhoven and its surroundings (800.000 inhabitants). This area is heavily focused on improving its accessibility by bike and sees the most rapid growth and highest demand for liveable housing space of all of Brabant. The focus of the pilot is on a city & region scale and the size of the Brainport region and its bicycle highways allows for looking at longer distance bike travel. Currently these movements are done by car, so studying how to turn these into bike movements can serve as a possible starting point.

Figure 7: The Brainport Region within the Province of North Brabant (Etil Research Group, 2019)

As part of the GPS data gathering scheme that sets off this pilot, different citizen panels, such as the SmartwayZ reizigerspanel or the OV-Reizigersoverleg, funded by but independent from the province will be contacted. These panels are contacted periodically through mailing lists with surveys on travel behaviour or specific target group matters, such as the experience of the elderly population. The call for a citizen observatory can be dispersed through a similar mail request or survey. Interested and invested citizens participating in the panels can choose to join the citizen observatory that explores the decision-making process around the transition to bike use and gathers data on the actual use of the bike. In order to map the decision-making process in as much detail as possible, the citizen observatories should contain a variety of stakeholders, ranging from invested citizens -bikers or non-bikers - to employers with a stake in mobility.

Citizens will use a variety of digital and non-digital methods, such as a possible mobile app, to gather qualitative and quantitative data such as their mobility routes, their origins and destination, transportation mode, travel time, and purpose, but also choice considerations or affective appraisals. This bottom-up micro data will be added by the pilot partners into a digital twin, capable of visualising the gathered data and combining it with other datasets. During the project the digital twin will also be further equipped with mobility data and a set of specific indicators that can be used to evaluate policy goals and possible macro data in the form of satellite or census data. The aggregation of these different layers can contextualise the (non-)biking behaviour of the citizen observatory, highlight salient correlations, and identify missing data sets or insights.

The qualitative data can be gathered through periodically survey the citizen observatory on their decision-making process, easily facilitated by the mobile app. This however targets the digitally inclined participants, and alternative communication channels have to be set up to include all members of the observatory. These surveys will help to get an idea why certain modalities are chosen for which trips and why certain routes are taken. Especially this understanding of the choices and influencing factors allow for co-creation of a policy approach that facilitates the shift to sustainable transport.

The pilot project is supported with the Argaleo DigiTwin a data aggregation and visualisation tool that can be used to support governance decision making. This digital tool already contains detailed data shared by municipalities (such as traffic, and traffic light data) and transporters (such as bus performances), the micro data of routing and citizen preferences gathered by the citizen observatories can be combined and visualised. The data will be analysed and visualized to generate insights and recommendations for facilitating the transition to bike use on regional and urban routes, as well as its associated neighbourhood improvements, to make them more liveable and sustainable.

These discussions will involve the citizen observatories into areas of governance, thus requiring a multidisciplinary team of experts, including data scientists, software developers, transportation planners, and community engagement specialists, to ensure a participatory and user-centred approach. Together with these groups, the province can assess focal points for campaigns to improve biking, either through advertising, spatial interventions, or stakeholder involvement such as employers. By including the citizen in the exploration of the topic and giving insight into the breaking points for their decision, the pilot introduces citizens to the data driven decision making process and involves them in a more bidirectional governance in order to solve problems deemed more relevant to the pilot community. These insights can provide useful insights to public administration for interventions and/or policy making.

4.3.4 Stakeholders

The stakeholders in the Nord Brabant Pilot include:

- The Province of Noord Brabant with its policy agenda and decision-making process that is now complemented with a more intensive interaction with citizens;
- Citizen Panels who are informed on mobility matters and consist of involved citizens of whom some can form a citizen observatory (e.g., SmartwayZ reizigerspanel, Ov-reizigerspanel, KBO-Brabant);
- Local organizations, such as local businesses, whose company policy can facilitate the switch to biking;
- Citizen observatories consisting of citizens, and domain experts from advisory organizations dealing with, for instance, accessibility, mobility, and citizen participation (e.g., Brainport Bereikbaar, Wij zijn Zet);
- Researchers and scientists who study mobility, citizen participation, and urban design (e.g., Breda University of Applied Sciences; Logistics Community Brabant);

Technology companies such as Argaleo and Mobidot whose data gathering and visualisation tool will form the backbone for policy directions and citizen involvement.

4.3.5 Pilot Pre-Conditions

GREENGAGE Engine must be linked with the Argaleo DigiTwin, which contains already data shared by municipalities.

4.3.6 Pilot Post-Conditions

Data gathered and insight produced within the project, will be available to help policy making and set up future targeted campaigns to sustain bike travels.

4.3.7 Use Cases

Table 3 lists the use cases finalised for North Brabant. Detailed requirements are listed in Table 13 and Table 14.

Table 3: List of use cases finalised for North Brabant. IDs are auto-generated by Planio

#	Priority	Subject	Description
708	Low	Facilitate sustainable transport in areas of mobility poverty	<p>In the North Brabant pilot, the first phase focuses on gathering mobility data (GPS tracking) from multimodal users. This data will be integrated into the DigiTwin platform, where the mobility patterns (routes, intensities, modalities) can be overlaid on existing datasets. One of such datasets is the coverage areas of the public transport in the North Brabant Region. Identifying which areas see very little bike use and are not covered by public transport will highlight several areas of interest where a CO can dive into the deterrents into biking. Managing these deterrents can remove the disconnect of these areas from the mobility system.</p> <p>Within these areas, and their associated COs, observers can subsequently give insight into their decision making process (interviews and surveys). Identifying specific obstacles (like infrastructure missing, safety, lack of service, travel time or cost, etc.) can then be logged and appraised with the help of different technologies.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure elements: Mindearth • Unsafe elements: Greengage app or Mindearth • Travel time: Travel Diary
540	High	Investigate deterrents for bike usage	<p>Collect quantitative (such as the number of trips by bike, trip distances by car or bike etc.) and qualitative (such as decision models, people's opinions, etc.) data to generate insights on shifting to sustainable transports, and identify obstacles to the use of bikes as the primary mean of transport. Data about citizens' experiences and decisions on using transport could be gathered through periodical surveys; next to these data, georeferenced data on physical obstacles around the region preventing the use of the bike could be gathered through digital apps.</p> <p>Investigate road maintenance (physical condition of the road, obeying safety and accessibility standards set by the CROW) as key deterrent for bike travel</p> <p>Qualitative exploration of the shared understanding of the term 'maintenance' (potential linkage with UWE LLMs).</p> <p>Identify the different dimensions of maintenance that are experienced as deterrent in measurable criteria</p> <p>Requirement:</p> <p>A list of measurable criteria for road maintenance</p> <p>The measurable criteria for maintenance (think of the form of consumption (probably x,y coordinates with description)</p> <p>Display the status of the measured criteria for maintenance on a map</p> <p>The possibility to create a flowchart or organogram</p>

539	Normal	Analyse multimodal travel patterns	<p>Use GPS or Other data sources, data to understand vehicular travel patterns, such as route choices and road network quality.</p> <p>Part of the Multimodal Traffic Mapping Project; Sjees data within the digitwin; PowerBI data report</p> <p>Showcases priority roads, oft used bike roads, missing links in bike infrastructure.</p> <p>(What is the data flow/output supposed to be like and how is it supposed to be consumed)</p> <p>REQUIREMENTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can identify short car trips which can steer future analysed bike links • Display identified car trips on map • Identify bike routes and paths with high intensity or frequency • Display identified bike routes and paths on a map
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4.4 Gerace Innovation Pilot

4.4.1 Background and Context

Gerace is an Italian town in the Province of Reggio Calabria, in the Region of Calabria (shown in Figure 8). It is one of the most beautiful villages in Italy and extends over 28.6 km² and has 2,399 inhabitants, of which 1,202 males and 1,197 females. The population density is 97 inhabitants per km² in the municipality. In the vicinity of the municipalities of Agnana Calabra, Portigliola i Canolo, Gerace is located 46 km southeast of Vibo Valentia, the largest city in the vicinity. Situated at an altitude of 500 metres, the municipality of Gerace has the following geographical coordinates 38° 16' 16" North, 16° 13' 12" East. Gerace is a municipality in the Aspromonte National Park.

The pilot activity in the municipality of Gerace considers the opportunity to exploit the synergy with the initiative led by the same municipality through the 20-million-euro Next Generation fund, for the EU recovery and resilience plan in support of the objectives of the EU Green Deal for sustainable city regeneration. A pilot action to be implemented by 2026 involving citizens in data monitoring for the DNSH (Do No Significant Harm) principle.

The overall project called "The door of the sun" (Figure 9) is made up of 9 interventions aimed at regenerating, repopulating and enhancing the great heritage of history, art, culture and traditions of the village, making it a shared wealth.

Figure 8: View of Gerace CC BY-SA author: [Attilios](#) under Wikipedia

The Greengage pilot action will combine citizen observatory data with collected satellite data in order to increase the analytical capacity for the implementation of pilot area regeneration program.

The overall work will aim at urban regeneration by developing a replicable system for DNSH.

The GREENGAGE pilot activities in Gerace directly align with the DNSH principle by prioritizing sustainable urban regeneration through environmentally responsible practices. By integrating citizen observatory data (e.g., air quality sensors and mobility analysis) with satellite imagery, the project ensures minimal environmental impact while addressing key local challenges. These efforts focus on improving air quality, enhancing infrastructure, and supporting decision-making with replicable solutions, all designed to prevent harm to ecosystems and adhere to the DNSH framework.

Table 4: Relationship between the Citizens’ Observatory and the application of the DNSH principle

Activity of the Citizen Observatory	Specific contribution to the DNSH Principle
Air Quality Monitoring (through ATMOTUBE PRO sensors and web interface)	Citizens collect data on polluting emissions and the presence of particulate matter. This data can support interventions to reduce emissions, respecting the DNSH by limiting air pollution.
Mobility data collection (through Open data and Dashcam)	By mapping traffic flows and identifying alternative routes, sustainable mobility methods are promoted, contributing to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.
Local emissions analysis	By comparing the data collected with regulatory standards, the Observatory can identify and propose solutions to mitigate environmental pollution, ensuring interventions compliant with the DNSH principle.

Community awareness	Educational activities aimed at citizens increase environmental awareness and promote practices that respect the DNSH principle, such as waste reduction and the use of environmentally friendly means of transport.
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Figure 9: Main image of the presentation of the project "Door of the sun" (the local project in synergy with GREENGAGE)

4.4.2 Goals and Objectives

The aim of this pilot project is to generate knowledge on how the increased awareness of citizens about the phenomena related to urban regeneration can contribute to a better and strengthened sustainable governance in a model medieval village, already member of the Most Beautiful Villages in Italy. This means that it meets the requirements relating to the specific ISO 9001 certification relating to "services aimed at enhancing, maintaining and recovering the national cultural heritage of memories and monuments, and at promoting tourism in the participating Municipalities".

Considering the indicators established by the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle which provide that the interventions envisaged by the national PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan) do not cause any significant damage to the environment, the project intends to support a citizens' observatory in monitoring the DNSH indicators (<https://www.italiadomani.gov.it/en/Interventi/dnsh.html>) so that the community can actively participate in monitoring and evaluating the impact of various activities and projects in their area and hold responsible parties accountable for any negative impacts.

Citizens' observatories can provide valuable insights and data that can help decision-makers to identify and address any DNSH issues. Furthermore, the involvement of citizens in the monitoring process can promote transparency and accountability and increase community trust in decision-making processes.

The indicators considered of greatest interest to the community of the Municipality of Gerace are based both on the specific context conditions and on the basis of the project financed with a budget of 20 million euros from the PNRR and which is divided into 9 targeted interventions that will respond to the needs of the community and the visitor/tourist.

First of all, at the context level, the importance of promoting awareness of the phenomena of hydrogeological instability is underlined considering the historical series recorded in the municipal area

of Gerace (south-eastern Calabria) and the ability to analyse the risks of degradation of the historical-artistic heritage connected triggering these phenomena. The analysis of previous events and the current conditions of the inhabited centre carried out also considering the interventions carried out to protect the buildings, allows to draw indications on the most probable types of expected instability, in the various sectors of the inhabited area, on the occasion of extreme rain events and could provide a replicable model for other municipalities with similar morphological characteristics.

Furthermore, on the basis of the "Gerace porta del sole" project, the prevailing values relating to the works envisaged in the inhabited centre can be monitored from the city observatory, favouring participatory environmental monitoring capable of including the monitoring of air quality and water, noise levels, waste management practices, biodiversity conservation and social impacts on local communities. Citizens can monitor and report these indicators through various means, such as surveys, sensor networks and community mapping exercises and resilience of the community, favouring the replicability of the experience in other villages in Italy and Europe. Overall, supporting a citizens' observatory to monitor DNSH indicators can promote more inclusive and participatory decision-making processes and improve the sustainability and resilience of communities.

An efficient system for the collection and analysis of the above-mentioned indicators could be considered in order to provide value-added participatory monitoring for territorial governance. The specific objectives of the pilot project can be summarized as:

- 1) Develop a training activity aimed at training citizens and stakeholders who will join the citizen observatory;
- 2) Develop a web application and interface that allows citizens to report values for relevant DNSH entries intuitively and securely.
- 3) Collect, validate, and aggregate data relating to DNSH indicators identified and linked to the works foreseen by the PNRR project through a secure and scalable back-end database and in a processing engine.
- 4) Analyse and visualize aggregated data to generate insights and recommendations to improve the sustainable and inclusive governance system.
- 5) Promote the altruistic work of citizens through recognition action, social networking features and feedback mechanisms and suggestions to incentivize citizens themselves to provide high-quality data
- 6) Evaluate compliance with the municipal project planning.

4.4.3 Pilot Specification

The pilot activity focuses on assisting the Municipality of Gerace in developing a Local Sustainable Mobility Action Plan. Using citizen-generated data from the Gerace Citizen Observatory, the initiative will enhance the monitoring of DNSH principles in the "Gerace Porta del Sole" project. This larger revitalization effort aims to regenerate the cultural, economic, and social fabric of Gerace by leveraging its territorial identity as a cultural attraction. The project includes improving accessibility, restoring buildings, providing cultural and tourist services, and fostering entrepreneurship, benefiting both Gerace and the Calabria region. It is therefore about creating synergy between the GREENGAGE project and the "Gerace Porta del Sole" initiative. By aligning GREENGAGE's focus on sustainable mobility and citizen engagement with the broader revitalization goals of "Porta del Sole," both efforts can complement each other. The Local Sustainable Mobility Action Plan, developed with citizen input, strengthens the adherence to DNSH principles, while the "Porta del Sole" project enhances Gerace's cultural, economic, and social development. This collaboration maximizes the impact on Gerace and the wider Calabria region. In specify the regeneration project in Gerace called "Gerace, door of the sun" has as its purpose the cultural, economic and social regeneration of the village by focusing on the territorial identity which becomes a cultural attraction to build a model of economic development, a generator of employment and attractiveness residential. A series of interventions are envisaged aimed at the recovery and enhancement of buildings, at improving the accessibility of the village, at the provision of tourist, cultural and entertainment services, training and incentives for businesses. All these actions will have an impact not only on Gerace but throughout the Calabria Region.

Table 5 shows a comparison table between the 9 targeted interventions under “**Gerace porta del sole” project**”, the DSNH reference related to these interventions, and finally, actions of added value and therefore considered of greater interest from the point of view of the Greengage project:

Table 5: Mapping targeted interventions to DNSH principles

Gerace Porta Del Sole" Project Intervention	DSNH Reference	Greengage Added Value
<p>Artinborgo festival (600 thousand euros): the festival "the enchanted village: street art in the alleys" which has been held since 1999 will be strengthened with further events aimed at enhancing the historical and architectural heritage, the local production system and the identity participatory place.</p>	<p>Criterion no. 1: Climate change mitigation</p>	<p>Monitoring of air quality and water, noise levels, waste management practices, sustainable mobility, biodiversity conservation and social impacts on local communities.</p>
<p>Mediterranean Creativity Hub (1.5 Million Euros): two laboratories are planned, the first for restoration, where the cultural heritage of the village will become a laboratory for young people, universities, academies of fine arts and local associations; the second of craftsmanship which aims to be a place of study, research and learning of artisan manufacturing traditions.</p>	<p>Criterion no. 4 Transition to the circular economy also with reference to waste reduction and recycling.</p> <p>An economic activity must not lead to significant inefficiencies in the use of recovered or recycled materials, to increases in the direct or indirect use of natural resources, to a significant increase in waste, to its incineration or disposal, causing significant environmental damage in the long term.</p>	<p>as above</p>
<p>Tourism Training Hub (600 Thousand Euros): recovery and adaptation of the former slaughterhouse premises and the external space of the cloister of the convent of the church of San Francesco d'assisi to be used as an open space for events, workshops, networking and training courses for tour leaders.</p>	<p>Criterion no.5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution</p> <p>Sheet 2 - Restructuring and redevelopment of residential and non-residential buildings.</p>	<p>Monitoring of quality of life and social impacts on local communities</p>
<p>Widespread Hotel (7.7 Million Euros) reuse and adaptation of homes with the creation of 160 luxury beds, wellness spa services and co-working with "art space" in which each room/space also</p>	<p>Criterion no.1 Climate change mitigation</p> <p>Sheet 2 - Restructuring and redevelopment of residential and non-residential buildings.</p>	<p>Monitoring of air quality and water, noise levels, waste management practices, biodiversity conservation and social impacts on local communities as well as mobility patterns.</p>

becomes a place for art exhibitions.

Physical Accessibility (3 Million Euros): facilitated access to the village for vehicular traffic limitation in the historic centre.

Criterion no.1 Climate change mitigation and Criterion no.5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution
 As above
 Sheet 18 - Creation of infrastructures for personal and cycle logistics mobility.

Integrated Lighting System (800 Thousand Euros): decorative and artistic lighting systems for monuments.

Criterion no.1 Climate change mitigation and Criterion no.5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution.
 As above
 Sheet 28 - Terrestrial connections and street lighting.

Gerace Digital Door (600 Thousand Euros): digital services for the use of the artistic and cultural heritage.

Criterion no.5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution
 As above
 Sheet 8 - Data centres.

Incentives For Development (4 Million Euro): incentives for SMEs and new female and youth enterprises and third sector enterprises operating in the cultural, artistic, tourism, recreational and social fields.

Criterion no.5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution
 As above
 Multi-sheets

Territorial Marketing (1.2 Million Euros): proposal for candidacy of the village as a UNESCO heritage site; training and capacity building activities to improve the expressed and unexpressed potential of the territory and tourist reception; communication and promotion of craft and tourism resources.

Criterion no.5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution
 As above
 Sheet 18 - Creation of infrastructures for personal and cycle logistics mobility.

Sustainable regeneration is a complex process that involves multiple aspects of social, economic, and environmental sustainability. To evaluate the success of a sustainable regeneration process, both qualitative and quantitative data must be considered.

In the participatory process, specifics may emerge relating to the best combinations between sensors that the Greengage project will be able to provide and an implementation strategy for the pilot case.

Here are some examples of data that can be used for evaluation:

Qualitative Data:

- Stakeholder engagement: one of the most critical components of sustainable regeneration is stakeholder engagement. Gathering qualitative data through surveys, interviews, and focus groups with stakeholders can provide valuable insights into the Gerace community's perception of the regeneration process.

- **Community wellbeing:** regeneration projects should aim to improve the quality of life of the community. Qualitative data can be collected on the community's health, safety, access to services, and overall wellbeing.
- **Social cohesion:** regeneration projects should strive to bring the community together and promote social cohesion. Qualitative data can be collected on the community's sense of belonging, trust, and social connections.

Quantitative Data:

- **Economic indicators:** sustainable regeneration should have a positive impact on the local economy. Quantitative data such as employment rates, income levels, and business growth can help to evaluate the economic impact of regeneration.
- **Environmental indicators:** regeneration projects should aim to reduce their environmental impact and promote sustainable practices. Quantitative data such as carbon emissions, energy consumption, and waste reduction can help to evaluate the environmental impact of regeneration.
- **Housing and infrastructure:** regeneration projects often involve the construction or renovation of housing and infrastructure. Quantitative data such as the number of new homes built, the number of renovated properties, and the quality of new infrastructure can help to evaluate the success of the regeneration process.

Overall, a combination of qualitative and quantitative data can help to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the sustainable regeneration process in Gerace (Figure 10). The data should be analysed and interpreted in the context of the project's goals and objectives, with a focus on identifying areas for improvement and opportunities for future development.

Figure 10: Gerace Pilot area

To engage citizens and incentivize them to submit high-quality and frequent data, the system to be developed could provide social networking features, such as discussion forums and user profiles, and feedback and suggestion mechanisms, such as a suggestion box or a feedback form. The system will also provide incentives, such as badges, points or prizes, to encourage citizens to participate in the project.

Multiple expertise will be required for this project: data science, software development, transport planning knowledge, and community engagement. The pilot will also give the opportunity to citizens to design other relevant experiments and solutions to solve further community problems.

Pilot success will be evaluated on its capacity to engage citizens, as well as collecting representative data and generated useful insights and recommendations.

4.4.4 Stakeholders

Stakeholders in the Gerace Urban Regeneration pilot project include:

- 1) **public institutions:** Gerace municipality, Calabria region.
- 2) **organized groups:** local association
- 3) **unorganized groups:** citizens of the Gerace municipality, local businesses etc

4.4.5 Pilot pre-conditions

The new technologies must be connected to the citizens' involvement platform which will be indicated by the Municipality of Gerace.

4.4.6 Pilot post-conditions

The data collected through the pilotage must be made available as open data, free of charge and reusable, through the open data portal of the cities involved, and following the AgiD (Agency for Digital Italy) guidelines on the formation, management and conservation of IT documents which contribute to the definition of the Interoperability Model of the Public Administration.

4.4.7 Use Cases

Table 6 lists the use cases finalised for Gerace valley. Detailed requirements are listed in Tables Table 15 and Table 16.

Table 6: List of finalised use cases for Gerace. The IDs are auto-generated.

#	Priority	Subject	Description
581	Normal	Analyse citizens' usage of public spaces and determine attractiveness of public spaces.	Use GPS data or local data from LTA , or other techniques, and analyse the usage profile of public areas. Identify spaces or areas that are the most used and the least used during different times of the day of the year.
538	Normal	Participatory environmental monitoring	<p>Monitor environmental data, such as air quality. Citizens would capture such data using portable sensors, analyse and visualise it using a shared platform, and identify sustainable improvements.</p> <p>Can Copernicus data be used for this? What data, if any? For example, understanding hydrogeological instability.</p> <p>Can UrbanTEP be used to visualise the data instead of a digital twin?</p> <p>Citizens should be able to perform interactive analyses. Bidirectional communication with citizens is very important.</p> <p>What kind of interactive analyses might be required?</p> <p>How often should it be monitored? Weekly, daily, hourly etc?</p> <p>What type of questions might be asked for the technology solution?</p>

4.5 Turano Valley Innovation Pilot

4.5.1 Background and Context

The Turano valley is located north-east of the city of Rome, on the first hills that rise about fifty kilometres from the urban settlement of the capital. It is bordered on its eastern side by the mountain range which can be considered as a continuation of the Simbruini mountains, i.e. that of the Carseolani mountains, which have the highest peak at 1,508 meters of Monte Navegna and on the western side by the eastern offshoots of the Sabine mountains, on average less elevated than the Carseolani (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: The Turano Valley (© OpenStreetMap, Administrative Boundaries: © EuroGeographics)

There are 17 villages that are part of it, and, on the basis of the geographical characterization within the valley, we group them into the following 3 groups:

- The villages that dominate and overlook the Turano Lake: Ascrea, Castel di Tora, Colle di Tora, Paganico Sabino, Posticciola.
- The villages gravitating along the road “Via Salaria”: Belmonte, Casaprota, Monteleone Sabino, Poggio Moiano e Torricella Sabina.
- The innermost villages: Collalto, Collegiove, Longone, Nespolo, Pozzaglia, Rocca Sinibalda e Turania.

The valley is characterized above all by the Turano Lake, located at 536 m. above sea level, along the course of the Turano River which is about ten kilometres long and has a perimeter of about 36 km. The artificial basin created in Terni, between the years 1935-1939 through the construction of a dam over 80 meters high, which blocks a reservoir with a capacity of over 150 million cubic meters of water connected to the twin reservoir of Salto by an approximately 9 km long tunnel, whose waters serve to feed powerful hydroelectric plants which supply important industries, first of all those of Terni. The lake extends at the foot of the nature reserve of Mount Navegna/Cervia (1506 m), a nature reserve covered by woods, and is characterized by the presence on its shores of ancient villages and castles which are reflected in the clear waters.

The economy of the villages of the Valle del Turano is based on rural resources, on some craft businesses and on tourism. The Turano Valley area covers a geographical area of 322.14 km² and has 10,250 inhabitants (5,283 males and 4,967 females). A very high naturalistic and landscape value also corresponds to great difficulties deriving from the roughness of the territory and its morphology. The territorial context is also characterized by numerous other critical issues such as:

- Inadequacy of the road infrastructure system;
- Absence of integrated public transport for the connection of the Municipalities of the Area;

- The need for a broadband network both as a function of social equalization and with the aim of adapting territorial competitiveness to that of the rest of the regional territory
- Depopulation phenomena;
- Constant increase in the elderly population;
- Inadequacy of health services in the face of growing needs;
- Absence of job opportunities;
- Low income;
- Low level of schooling among the youth population;
- A constant growth of both "secular" and religious excursion tourism which requires an adequate supply of services.

4.5.2 Pilot Specification

The pilot project has the objective of addressing, in particular, two of the critical elements mentioned above, namely the inadequacy of the road infrastructure system and the phenomenon of the progressive depopulation of the villages, which in Italy has reached -289,000 residents in the villages with less of 10 thousand inhabitants in the period 1951-2019, and promote an urban revitalization that requires careful territorial planning and services. The pilot project targets 2 Green Deal areas: 'Area 1: Increasing climate ambition: Cross-sectoral challenges' and 'Area 10 - Empowering citizens for the transition to a climate-friendly and sustainable Europe.

A citizen observatory dedicated to contribute to contrasting depopulation and studying people's mobility (Mobility Data Analysis) by combining:

- the analysis of data on mobility;
- the services for remote working;
- the initiative of urban regeneration;

will be able to provide valuable information to support decisions in order to identify strategies and models for regeneration and improvement of mobility, based on citizens' preferences.

This activity could contribute to corroborate the development of more sustainable and efficient transport policies and infrastructures. The Valle del Turano area, an hour from Rome, can in fact count on the important opportunities deriving from the spread of working from home caused by the pandemic, which has freed workers from larger centres to smaller ones. Satellite data and data collected through the active participation of citizens will be used to increase the analytical capacity regarding mobility and quality of life (Services, Economy, Infrastructure, Environment, Culture, Quality of social and institutional processes).

4.5.3 Goals and Objectives

The objectives of the initiative linked to the citizens' observatory are in synergy with the project of "*Cultural and social regeneration of small historic villages*" launched in the Valle del Turano area (2022-2026) through funds from the PNRR and led by the municipality of Paganico Sabino.

This synergy has the main purpose of counteracting the phenomenon of depopulation, improving liveability and strengthening the attractive potential of the villages; to achieve this goal, the action of retrieving, collecting and analysing data, with the contribution of citizens, will be of fundamental.

The phenomenon of depopulation is a complex issue that can have various causes, such as economic changes, environmental factors, or demographic shifts. Combining mobility data analysis, remote working services, and urban regeneration involving stakeholders can be an effective strategy to address depopulation, but it is important to ensure that these efforts are coordinated and integrated with other initiatives to achieve the desired impact.

Mobility data analysis involves analysing patterns of movement and travel using data from sources such as GPS devices, mobile phones, and transportation systems. This can provide insights into how people move and interact with different areas, which can help policymakers and planners make more informed decisions about how to allocate resources and plan for future growth.

Remote working services, which allow people to work from anywhere, can be an attractive option for individuals who want to live in a depopulating area but still have access to job opportunities and professional networks. This can help attract and retain residents, especially those who are looking for a better work-life balance.

Urban regeneration involving stakeholders refers to a collaborative process of revitalizing urban areas through the involvement of local residents, businesses, and community groups. This can help to create more attractive and liveable neighbourhoods, improve access to services and amenities, and enhance social cohesion and community pride.

4.5.4 Stakeholders

Stakeholders in the Turano pilot project include:

- 1) **public institutions:** Turano municipality.
- 2) **organized groups:** local associations
- 3) **unorganized groups:** citizens of the Turano municipality, local businesses etc.

4.5.5 Pre-Conditions

Mobility and other associated data is available.

4.5.6 Post-Conditions

The analyses and other data generated by the GREENGAGE tools are integrated with existing systems and available in formats that can be integrated with other systems.

4.5.7 Use Cases

Table 7 lists the use cases finalised for Gerace valley. Detailed requirements are listed in Tables Table 17 and Table 18.

Table 7: List of use cases for Turano. The IDs are auto-generated by Planio.

#	Priority	Subject	Description
754	Normal	Participatory environmental monitoring	<p>Monitor environmental data such as air quality, noise levels, waste management, etc. Citizens would capture such data using portable sensors; then analyse and visualise them using a shared platform to identify sustainable improvements.</p> <p>Can Copernicus data be used for this? What data, if any?</p> <p>Can UrbanTEP be used to visualise the data instead of a digital twin?</p> <p>Citizens should be able to perform interactive analyses. Bidirectional communication with citizens is very important.</p> <p>What kind of interactive analyses might be required?</p> <p>How often should it be monitored? Weekly, daily, hourly etc?</p>

			<p>What type of questions might be asked for the technology solution?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse hydrogeological instability Gather opinions from people regarding various topics such as the construction of an elevator during summer months to facilitate a high number of tourists. Heat waves during the summer -> impact on livability. <p>Mobility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Safety of roads -> use cameras mounted on commuters. No of accidents, potholes or broken roads, no of cars, traffic flow. Diurnal traffic analysis? Different times of day? Traffic is always higher in one direction and less in the opposite.
580	Normal	Analyse citizens' usage of public spaces and determine attractiveness of public spaces.	Use GPS data , or other techniques, and analyse the usage profile of public spaces (parks, shops, etc). Identify spaces that are the most used and the least used during different times of the day.
578	Normal	Mobility pattern analysis to determine accessibility to shops, schools, services and other local amenities	Use techniques such as app-based location or GPS tracking to determine routes that citizens take to local amenities and identify improvements. Categorise routes by mode of transport and analyse alternative travel modes.

5 Innovation Pilot Specification Analysis

Table 8 shows a comparison of the various innovation pilots, how they incorporate co-design as well as their relevant to the GREENGAGE objectives.

Table 8: Cross-comparison of GREENGAGE pilot specifications.

INNOVATION PILOT	PILOT SUMMARY	CO-DESIGN ASPECT	RELEVANCE TO GREENGAGE OBJECTIVES
BRISTOL	Create Liveable Neighbourhoods that help improve local air quality, promote quality of life and healthy citizens. After initial co-design with citizens, Bristol is now looking to implement the outcomes of the co-design phase using temporary interventions in the neighbourhood in the first phase as an experiment, and more permanent interventions in the second phase.	A multi-phased co-design approach where citizens are consulted at every stage and help design the Liveable Neighbourhoods. The two phases are co-discover and co-develop.	GREENGAGE tools are expected to contribute in the two experimental phases and help involve citizens in data collection and monitoring using COs.
NORTH BRABANT	Use COs to promote active travel, including cycling and walking and understand why citizens choose to use motorised transportation. Developed by integrating various quantitative and qualitative data sources in a digital twin for analysis. Brabant has several existing tools.	Citizens will be involved in data collection through the use of various GREENGAGE technologies and will help to promote enhanced decision-making and to devise sustainable solutions.	GREENGAGE technologies will be used to co-design sustainable solutions with citizens by understanding their decisions concerning mobility and working with them to understand the impact of alternative mobility modes.
ØRESTAD, COPENHAGEN	Use citizen engagement to understand citizens' lived experience and identify opportunities for improvement. This will include understanding citizens' mobility needs and requirements including both local mobility and commuting.	Co-design approaches will be used to identify neighbourhood improvement plans validated with the citizens to ensure acceptability and appropriateness.	GREENGAGE tools will help collect citizen derived data and to deploy visualisation to help identify improvement potentials to and to ascertain their acceptability and feasibility.
GERACE	Aim to involve citizens in the CO in order to monitor the “do you no significant harm” principles and monitor various environmental factors such as waste, noise level, air quality etc.	Citizens are being involved primarily in a monitoring capacity.	GREENGAGE tools will help collect data from citizens and visualise this data to support the engagement of both citizens and policy-makers,

<p>TURANO VALLEY</p>	<p>Aim to promote understanding of citizens' mobility patterns as well as patterns of depopulation. Objective to understand what role urban regeneration and remote working can perform in reducing depopulation in the Turano Valley.</p>	<p>Citizens will help in providing mobility as well as urban regeneration data that can be used to understand the behaviour patterns in the Turano Valley.</p>	<p>enabling co-monitoring with the citizens.</p> <p>GREENGAGE tools will be used to help understand citizen's mobility patterns and noting, visualisation and analysis of the impacts of proposed improvements.</p>
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AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Overall, the innovation pilots demonstrate how COs can be used to promote sustainable and democratic solutions to policy challenges such as climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as healthy cities etc. In this regard, it is clear from the pilot specifications that **mobility is a major policy focus** that has particular relevance for the majority of innovation pilots and a central objective in delivering on the policy challenges identified above according to GREENGAGE objectives and the European Green Deal.

5.1 GREENGAGE Objectives and European Green Deal

The central driving force of GREENGAGE concerns engagement of citizens observatories allied with the mobilisation of technology solutions to deliver via urban and regional planning processes on the key objectives of the European Green Deal. The GREENGAGE innovation pilots perform a critical role in this process in defining, developing and delivering real-world urban planning engagement with the bottom of processes of citizen engagement according to local defined policy objectives for green transition that support the delivery of the European Green Deal.

The European Green Deal is a set of policy initiatives by the European Union (EU) aimed at achieving carbon neutrality and sustainable growth by 2050. In this context urban planning objectives are focused on creating sustainable and liveable cities that are resilient to climate change, promoting low-carbon lifestyles, and support sustainable economic growth. The principal urban planning objectives of the European Green Deal include:

- **Sustainable urban mobility:** The Green Deal aims to promote sustainable transport, including the development of low-carbon public transport systems, the creation of pedestrian zones and cycling networks, and the promotion of electric vehicles.
- **Climate-resilient cities:** The Green Deal aims to build climate-resilient cities that are better prepared for the impacts of climate change, such as flooding and extreme weather events. This can be achieved through the use of green infrastructure, sustainable water management systems, and the development of adaptation strategies.
- **Green and blue infrastructure:** The Green Deal emphasizes the importance of green and blue infrastructure in cities, such as parks, green roofs, and water management systems. This can help to reduce the urban heat island effect, improve air quality, and provide urban ecosystems that support biodiversity.

5.2 Urban Planning and the European Green Deal

The European Green Deal recognizes the important role that cities play in achieving its climate goals. Cities are responsible for around 70% of greenhouse gas emissions and are therefore a critical area for action to achieve sustainable and resilient cities. Urban planning is a critical tool for attaining these goals. It can help to create compact and walkable urban environments that reduce the need for private car use and promote sustainable transport modes, such as walking, cycling, and public transport. Urban planning can also support the development of green spaces and sustainable urban infrastructure, such as renewable energy systems, green roofs, and rainwater harvesting.

5.3 15-minute Cities and the European Green Deal

The concept of 15-minute cities is identified as a critical opportunity to promote sustainable and liveable urban environments., where all essential services and amenities, such as shops, healthcare, schools, and public transport, are located within a 15-minute walk or bike ride from residents' homes. The European Green Deal supports the development of 15-minute cities as a way to promote sustainable and healthy urban living. It recognizes that compact and walkable cities can reduce the need for car travel and promote sustainable transport modes, which can reduce greenhouse gas emissions and improve air quality. In this respect the Green Deal calls for the development of sustainable urban mobility plans that promote walking, cycling, and public transport and reduce the use of private cars. It also supports the development of green spaces and the use of nature-based solutions, such as green roofs and urban forests, to improve urban living conditions and promote biodiversity.

6 Use Cases and Requirements Analysis

Tables Table 9–Table 18 show the functional and non-functional requirements for each pilot. There are a number of common use cases that apply to different innovation pilots. The key themes are environmental (air quality) monitoring, mobility analysis and public space usage across the different innovation pilots. For example, Bristol and Copenhagen are both interested in air quality monitoring, while Bristol, Copenhagen and Borghi are all interested in mobility pattern analysis (use case 12). This indicates that there are indeed cross-cutting challenges that the GREENGAGE Engine can help to solve. This is significant because for the common challenges same solutions can be replicated across different European cities. However, these solutions should have a flexible, extendable, and interoperable architecture for the development of bespoke features to fulfil specific needs and use case requirements of different citizen observatories. Furthermore, the use cases and requirements will also be used to derive relevant KPIs for success.

Table 9: List of finalised functional requirements for Bristol.

#	Priority	Subject	Associated use case	Description
823	Normal	Perform sentiment classification on the textual perceived views	535	Efficiency in analysing textual/survey data
822	High	Apply text summarisation to create a summary of perceived views provided by citizens	535	To make the analysis more efficient, apply summarization models
819	Normal	Analyse the impact of planning interventions by determining how these interventions have impacted peoples' mobility behaviour to local amenities	536	Mobility patterns and impact assessment
818	Normal	Analyse how people travel to local amenities like shops, schools, hospitals etc.	536	Find out transport mode used for local travelling.
817	High	Collect and analyse peoples' perceived view on safety of the roads, area etc.	535	Safety should be measured based on both quantitative (or auto detection) as well as qualitative data/inputs. User surveys highlighting Pols, roads, areas (e.g., polygons) and their perceived safety levels ... The safety mainly include, road crossings, dark roads/low lighting, low lighting in public spaces like parks, anti-social behaviour, narrow kerbs/pedestrian walking space, traffic

				speed, parked cars on kerbs, no/malfunctioning CCTV, road surface suitability (e.g., potholes) for cycling, public transport/buses frequency etc.
816	High	Detect mode of mobility of peoples journeys	533	To find out what mode of transport people use for moving from point A to point B and what impact of planning interventions had on their journeys
815	Normal	System should identify correlation between post-trial scheme journeys and air quality, and present/visualise it in an easy to understand format	533	What impact of specific type of journeys can have on air quality in the area?
814	Normal	Capture blackcarbon data on selected streets and/or specific locations, and visualise whether its good or bad	534	black carbon data will add value to existing data repositories of BCC
812	Normal	GREENGAGE tech should be able to help in finding out the impact of Trial scheme interventions on quality of journeys people make?	533	How trail scheme interventions are impacting peoples journeys? Are they taking longer route? Are they prioritising walking, cycling or other sustainable modes of mobility? Are they feeling safe in low traffic roads when making journeys? How is this impacting different types of users/stakeholders e.g., delivery drivers, school children, elderly people, commuters, local businesses, etc.?
811	Normal	Calculate quality of journeys people make by using different modes of transport and at different times of a day	533	Related to #810 , Are people making journey by using a specific mode of transport because they do not have alternative choice? Or it is because of environmental, health and financial reasons? the quality could be related to how satisfied people are with the time taken to reach to their destination? safety or liveability of streets they used to reach to their destination? Quality of

				footpaths, cycle paths, or roads? public transport's timely availability and accessibility? etc. the overall cost of the journey?
810	High	Detect , analyse and visualise how people are making their journeys	533	This requirement is about mode detection to find out what mode of transport people use to make shorter and longer journeys. How their behaviour changes during different times of a day (e.g., morning, afternoon, evening, night, school time)? How weather conditions make impact on their decisions e.g., rainy weather, sunny weather, cold or hot etc.
809	Normal	Privacy should be protected for any data collection and analysis of CO data	533	Privacy and data protection is mandatory for this use case
808	High	Calculate, compare and intuitively visualise street liveability index for pre-trial and post-trial phases	533	Street liveability Index / indicators (provided by UWE for WP4) should be used to determine liveability of streets. This would require various data sets already in BCC databases e.g., traffic counters, street restrictions/closures, interventions and missing data should be gathered, analysed and visualised through GG technologies (MindView, GREENGAGE App, Mode, UrbanTEP, Quality Dashboard, Superset etc)
806	Normal	Allow access to citizens' own data through interactive visualisation	534	Citizens should be able to see what data they have collected and this should be available through different interactive visual projections (e.g., maps, graphs etc).
803	Normal	Air quality simulation of street canyon by using Copernicus data	534	HOPU's air quality dashboard where air quality simulations are shown by using downscaled satellite data at street level should be integrated with the local (in-situ) data to provide a holistic air quality status of the EBLN.
801	Normal	Correlation of NO2 readings with traffic counters (data collected by BCC) to show variation in air quality when traffic is higher or lower	534	Correlation of NO2 readings with traffic counters (data collected by BCC) to show variation in air quality when traffic is higher or lower
800	Normal	Background concentrations should be clearly shown to avoid any misinterpretation of the results	534	Accuracy in data generated through traffic in EBLN is important to avoid confusion with pollution from other sources, therefore background concentrations should be clearly gathered and shown to avoid any misinterpretation of the results

799	Normal	Capture high quality NO2 data	534	NO2 data is more relevant for EBLN and high frequency of NO2 data has the potential to add value to already collected NO2 data through diffusion tubes deployed at major/certain roads of the EBLN.
798	Normal	Capturing air quality data through reliable mobile (or/and stationary) sensors on specific streets of EBLN	534	Air quality sensors must be calibrated regularly in close proximity of official air quality monitoring stations (the closest one is few miles away)
772	Normal	Automatic object detection and analysis through street images/videos	535	<p>Things to consider are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - poor lighting - road crossing - vehicle speed - inconsiderate or illegal parking - driver/cycling behaviour - crimes (anti social behaviour etc.) - littering - accessibility such level surfacing for people with disabilities - children height and vehicles parked can be a cause of hazard - under utilised or less surveillance routes - etc. <p>There are other street safety/health metrics:</p> <p>Motorised vehicle speed</p>

				<p>Volume of motorised traffic</p> <p>Mix of vehicles</p> <p>Cycle safety at junctions</p> <p>Ease of crossing side roads</p> <p>Ease of crossing between junctions</p> <p>Priority of crossing at junctions</p> <p>Navigation of crossings for people with visual impairments</p> <p>Space for walking</p> <p>Quality of the carriageway surface</p> <p>Space for cycling</p> <p>Lighting</p> <p>Reducing convenience of driving short journeys</p> <p>Some of the above might be possible to automatically detect and measure on the scale of 0 - 3 as indicated in this document - https://aitonline.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/HEUGREENGAGE337/Shared%20Documents/WP4%20CO%20enabling%20infrastructure%20and%20interoperable/GREEN%20Engine/Metrics/Bristol%20Pilot%20Metrics.docx?d=we4778df0ebd34fe8b72334d41c383456&csf=1&web=1&e=VjhC0t</p>
649	Normal	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering	536	Implement a mechanism to collect data on the usage of roads and sidewalks both from people passing by and from people standing in front of shops and other places.

		near shops or other amenities)		
622	Normal	Collect real-time GPS data	579	
607	High	Visualise mobility statistics using different parameters (traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, etc)	533	Provide visual representations and statistics of mobility-related data using various parameters such as traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, and other relevant factors.
606	Normal	Visualise mobility statistics using different parameters (traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, etc)	536	
602	Normal	Visualise mobility statistics using different parameters (traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, etc)	579	
594	Normal	Import air quality data in different formats (csv, json, etc)	534	
590	Normal	Export air quality data in standard formats (csv, json, etc)	534	Provide the capability to export air quality data collected by the system in standard formats such as CSV (Comma-Separated Values), JSON (JavaScript Object Notation), or other widely used formats.
563	Normal	Provide cross-cutting insights and analyses from various data sources		GREENGAGE tools should provide insights based on the analysis of different data sources to support dialogue between citizens. Please refer to attached image.
556	Normal	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering near shops or other amenities)	579	

550	High	Visualise in real-time perceived safety	535	
548	High	Import crime data in different formats	535	
545	Normal	Visualise change of air quality at different times of the day	534	
544	Normal	Visualise air quality across the city	534	Develop a visual representation of air quality data across different areas of the city, indicating pollutant levels, air quality indexes, and potential health risks.

Table 10: List of finalised non-functional requirements for Bristol.

ID	Priority	Subject	Parent issue	Description
881	Normal	Ensure data privacy/protection is fully implemented	754	Compliance to ethics protocols and GDPR/other relevant privacy and data protection regulations should be implemented properly
835	Normal	Ensure data privacy/protection is fully implemented	581	Compliance to ethics protocols and GDPR/other relevant privacy and data protection regulations should be implemented properly
828	Normal	Ensure data privacy/protection is fully implemented	538	Compliance to ethics protocols and GDPR/other relevant privacy and data protection regulations should be implemented properly
807	Normal	Ensure data privacy/protection is fully implemented	534	Compliance to ethics protocols and GDPR/other relevant privacy and data protection regulations should be implemented properly
805	Normal	Where appropriate, allow users to interact with the results through visual interface	534	Users should be able to filter results on selected features, e.g., day, month, year, pollutants, values at a selected point on map and see timeseries data etc.

804	Normal	User interface / visualisation of results are easy to interpret by end users/citizens	534	It is important that citizens should be able to clearly interpret results e.g., graph labelling is clear and understandable, context sensitive help to understand results e.g., Air Quality Index explained, even summary such as whether AQ on a specific point is bad or good, etc.
574	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should meet legal or regulatory requirements, such as GDPR or accessibility standards.		Compliance is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools comply with legal and regulatory requirements, such as GDPR or accessibility standards. The tools should be designed and implemented with compliance in mind, and they should be regularly audited and tested to ensure that they remains compliant.
573	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be easy to maintain, with clear documentation, modular code, and easy-to-understand architecture.		Maintainability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can be easily maintained and updated over time. The tools should have clear documentation, modular code, and an easy-to-understand architecture that allows developers to make changes and updates without introducing errors or breaking the system.
572	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be compatible with other systems, software, or hardware that they may need to interact with.		Compatibility is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can interact and work seamlessly with other systems, software, or hardware that they may need to interact with. The tools should be able to share data and communicate with other systems using standard protocols and formats.
571	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be user-friendly, with a clear and intuitive interface that is easy to use and understand by citizens observers.		Usability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools are easy to use and understand for users. The tools should have a clear and intuitive interface that is easy to navigate and use, even for non-technical users such as citizens observers. They should also be accessible to users with disabilities.
570	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should have appropriate levels of security measures in place to protect against unauthorized access, data breaches, or other security threats. Privacy and GDPR compliance is essential.		Security is a critical non-functional requirement that ensures that the software system is protected against unauthorized access, data breaches, and other security threats. The system should have appropriate security measures in place to prevent attacks, and it should comply with relevant privacy and data protection laws and regulations, such as GDPR.

569	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be able to handle increasing amounts of data, users, and traffic without impacting performance or reliability.		Scalability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENAGE tools can handle increasing amounts of data, users, or traffic without degrading performance or reliability. The tools should be able to scale up or down as needed, and they should be able to accommodate future growth without requiring major changes or upgrades.
568	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be available for use for a reasonable percentage of time and have a reasonable level of uptime, and should be able to recover from failures without losing data.		Reliability is another important non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools are available for use when needed. The tools must be able to operate continuously and reliably without downtime, and they should be able to recover from failures without losing any data.
567	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be able to handle a reasonable number of concurrent users, process a certain number of transactions per second, or respond to user requests within a reasonable time limit.		Performance is a crucial non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can handle the workload the workload that they are designed to handle. The tools must be able to respond to user requests quickly and efficiently without slowing down or crashing.

Table 11: List of finalised functional requirements for Copenhagen.

#	Priority	Subject	Parent issue	Description
845	Normal	Analyse where citizens are exposed to health hazards such as noise and air pollution	576	The GREENGAGE tools should help city administrations assess where citizens are most exposed to various health hazards such as noise and air pollution. This will allow the administrations to devise interventions to mitigate the effects of these hazards.
844	Normal	GREENGAGE tools should help validate data collected through GOs	576	GREENGAGE tools should provide methods and workflows to validate the data collected through GOs, e.g. by comparing against data from other sources.

843	Normal	Visualise noise pollution as a 3D heatmap	576	Noise pollution is usually measured 2.5m above ground. Normally this is adequate. However, in Copenhagen where there are tall buildings next to motorways, the noise pollution travels vertically upwards. Thus the noise levels in tall buildings next to motorways is unmonitored. GREENGAGE should provide mechanisms to allow city administrations to visualise and monitor these noise levels.
842	Normal	GREENGAGE technologies should provide a web interface for uploading citizen-collected data for further analysis and processing	537	A web interface should be available for uploading citizen-collected datasets as an alternative to the GREENGAGE apps.
728	Normal	Visualisation Tools	577	The system shall provide basic capabilities to visualise data, such as bar charts, pie charts, heatmaps, or trend lines.
727	Normal	Data Filtering	577	The system shall allow users to filter and sort data by various criteria (date range, location, route type, demographic information, etc.)
721	Normal	Comment/Discussion	577	The system shall provide a forum-like space for COBs to comment on specific data points, share experiences, and start conversations.
720	Normal	Accessibility Survey	577	The system shall include a survey for COBs to rate the accessibility of key amenities (schools, shops, etc.) along their routes.
719	Normal	Photo & Video Upload	577	The system shall allow COBs to upload photos and videos linked to specific locations or routes.
718	Normal	Route Mapping	577	The system shall display submitted routes visually on a map, allowing users to explore patterns and identify hotspots.
717	Normal	Data Submission	577	The system shall allow Citizen Observers (COBs) to submit mobility data in various formats, including GPS tracks, manual logs, and observations.
716	Normal	User Profiles	537	Enables users to maintain a profile with basic information (username, contact details if relevant, areas of interest). Profiles can be configured with privacy options to control what information is visible to others.
715	Normal	Authentication & Authorization	537	Secure login mechanisms to identify and verify citizen scientists, project team members, and potentially external collaborators, using either built-in user accounts or integration with existing authentication systems (e.g., social sign-in)

714	Normal	Filtering and Querying	537	Allows users to filter data based on specific criteria (e.g., date range, location, survey question responses) and to run basic queries to focus on particular subsets of interest.
712	Normal	Photo & Comment Submission	537	Allows users to submit photographs and written comments alongside their observations, adding qualitative insights and visual context.
711	Normal	Flexible Survey Builder	537	Provides tools enabling non-technical users to create and modify surveys with different question types, branching logic, and multimedia elements as needed.
709	Normal	Allow data to be synchronised offline	537	Enables data collection using dedicated apps or tools even when the user's device lacks internet connectivity. Data is stored locally and automatically synced to the project's database once a connection is restored.
642	High	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering near shops or other amenities)	577	
628	High	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering near shops or other amenities)	537	
625	High	Collect real-time GPS data	577	
623	High	Collect real-time GPS data	537	
619	High	Visualise environment data (noise levels, waste, water quality, etc)	576	Provide visual representations and statistics of environment-related data, including noise levels, waste management, water quality, and other relevant factors.
618	High	Collect environment data from portable sensors	576	Deploy portable sensors to collect environmental data such as temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise levels.
611	High	Export traffic analysis data	577	
605	High	Visualise mobility statistics using different parameters (traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, etc)	577	

603	High	Visualise mobility statistics using different parameters (traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, etc)	537	he chosen tools include built-in capabilities for generating basic statistics (e.g., averages, percentages, distributions), simple charts (bar charts, pie charts, timelines), and the ability to map data points.
596	High	Import historical mobility data	577	
592	Normal	Import air quality data in different formats (csv, json, etc)	575	
589	Normal	Export air quality data in standard formats (csv, json, etc)	575	
587	High	Visualise change of air quality at different times of the day	576	Provide a visual representation of the change in air quality levels at different times of the day within the city.
585	Normal	Visualise change of air quality at different times of the day	575	
584	High	Visualise air quality across the city as a heatmap	576	<p>City administrations should be able to visualise air quality across the city / district. The GREENGAGE tools should help city admins identify patterns and dynamics in the way air pollution spreads across the city / district.</p> <p>The dynamics of air pollution should be visualised as a time series correlated with traffic volume and flow.</p>
582	Normal	Visualise air quality across the city	575	
566	Normal	Visualise biodiversity changes across time	543	Provide visual representations that illustrate changes in biodiversity over time within the designated area.
565	Normal	Collect ground images of city greenery	543	Capture and collect ground-level images of city greenery, including parks, gardens, trees, and other vegetation, using appropriate imaging devices or tools.

564	Normal	Import satellite imagery	543	Enable the system to import satellite imagery data for the designated area.
563	Normal	Provide cross-cutting insights and analyses from various data sources		GREENGAGE tools should provide insights based on the analysis of different data sources to support dialogue between citizens. Please refer to attached image.
547	High	Import air quality data in different formats (csv, json, etc)	576	
546	High	Export air quality data in standard formats (csv, json, etc)	576	

Table 12: Table 9: List of finalised functional requirements for Copenhagen.

#	Priority	Subject	Parent issue	Description
841	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should support iOS devices	537	All GREENGAGE tools must support iOS devices for data collection, analysis, reporting etc.
726	Normal	Accessibility	577	The system shall meet accessibility guidelines for those with disabilities (visual impairment, motor difficulties, etc.)
725	Normal	Compatibility	577	The system shall be accessible on common web browsers and mobile operating systems.
724	Normal	Scalability	577	The system shall be able to handle increasing data volumes and user numbers as the project grows.
723	Normal	Data Security	577	The system shall implement appropriate security measures to protect user data privacy and prevent unauthorised access.
722	Normal	Usability	577	The system shall have a user-friendly interface with clear instructions, suitable for users with varying technical skills.
574	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should meet legal or regulatory requirements,		Compliance is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools comply with legal and regulatory requirements, such as GDPR or accessibility standards. The tools

		such as GDPR or accessibility standards.		should be designed and implemented with compliance in mind, and they should be regularly audited and tested to ensure that they remains compliant.
573	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be easy to maintain, with clear documentation, modular code, and easy-to-understand architecture.		Maintainability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can be easily maintained and updated over time. The tools should have clear documentation, modular code, and an easy-to-understand architecture that allows developers to make changes and updates without introducing errors or breaking the system.
572	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be compatible with other systems, software, or hardware that they may need to interact with.		Compatibility is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can interact and work seamlessly with other systems, software, or hardware that they may need to interact with. The tools should be able to share data and communicate with other systems using standard protocols and formats.
571	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be user-friendly, with a clear and intuitive interface that is easy to use and understand by citizens observers.		Usability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools are easy to use and understand for users. The tools should have a clear and intuitive interface that is easy to navigate and use, even for non-technical users such as citizens observers. They should also be accessible to users with disabilities.
570	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should have appropriate levels of security measures in place to protect against unauthorized access, data breaches, or other security threats. Privacy and GDPR compliance is essential.		Security is a critical non-functional requirement that ensures that the software system is protected against unauthorized access, data breaches, and other security threats. The system should have appropriate security measures in place to prevent attacks, and it should comply with relevant privacy and data protection laws and regulations, such as GDPR.
569	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be able to handle increasing amounts of data, users, and traffic without impacting performance or reliability.		Scalability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENAGE tools can handle increasing amounts of data, users, or traffic without degrading performance or reliability. The tools should be able to scale up or down as needed, and they should be able to accommodate future growth without requiring major changes or upgrades.
568	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be available for use		Reliability is another important non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools are available for use when needed. The tools must be able to operate continuously and

		for a reasonable percentage of time and have a reasonable level of uptime, and should be able to recover from failures without losing data.		reliably without downtime, and they should be able to recover from failures without losing any data.
567	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be able to handle a reasonable number of concurrent users, process a certain number of transactions per second, or respond to user requests within a reasonable time limit.		Performance is a crucial non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can handle the workload the workload that they are designed to handle. The tools must be able to respond to user requests quickly and efficiently without slowing down or crashing.

Table 13: List of functional requirements finalised for North Brabant. The IDs are auto-generated.

ID	Priority	Subject	Parent issue	Description
849	Low	Citizen Observer Management	708	System shall provide functionality to manage citizen observers including registration training activity tracking and contribution management. The system must support communication features and recognition mechanisms for active participants.
848	Low	Survey Management System	708	System shall provide functionality to create distribute and analyse surveys about mobility choices and barriers. The system must support multiple question types response validation and automated analysis of results.
847	Low	Route Appraisal System	708	System shall provide capabilities for users to assess and score routes based on predefined criteria including safety infrastructure quality and accessibility. The assessment must support both quantitative scoring and qualitative feedback.
846	Low	Deterrent Documentation System	708	System shall provide functionality for users to document mobility deterrents including infrastructure issues safety concerns and service gaps. Users must be able to upload photos add descriptions categorise issues and provide location data for each deterrent.
732	Normal	User Management & Access Control	539	The system shall implement a robust user management and authentication system with role-based permissions.

731	Normal	Integration with Digital Twin	539	The system shall provide seamless data transfer to the Argaleo DigiTwin platform for visualisation and integration with other datasets.
730	Normal	Multimodal Analysis Capabilities	539	The system shall support analysis techniques enabling the examination of movement patterns across different travel modes.
729	Normal	Multi-Source Data Collection	539	The system shall allow citizens to gather mobility data using a variety of methods, including GPS tracking (mobile app) and qualitative surveys.
670	High	Send questionnaires through GREENGAGE technologies	540	Enable the functionality to send questionnaires to users through the GREENGAGE technologies platform. This may be done through the Collaborative Environment from DEUSTO. Currently facilitated with Fietzersbond technology and methods, but will be contrasted with the GREENGAGE app.
664	High	Collect survey data on citizen experience of public transports	540	Implement a mechanism to collect survey data from citizens regarding their experience with public transportation services. May be implemented in the Collaborative Environment from DEUSTO
595	Normal	Import historical mobility data	539	
563	Normal	Provide cross-cutting insights and analyses from various data sources		GREENGAGE tools should provide insights based on the analysis of different data sources to support dialogue between citizens. Please refer to attached image.
562	Normal	Send questionnaires through GREENGAGE technologies	539	To study the modality choices and understand the conditions, asking users to fill in a question on their mode choice should be facilitated
561	High	Visualise statistics on bike users vs no-users	540	Provide visual representations and statistics comparing the number of bike users and non-users in the city.
560	High	Collect georeferenced data on physical obstacles for bike users	540	Capture and record georeferenced data on physical obstacles that may hinder or pose risks to bike users, such as potholes, road hazards, construction zones, or blocked bike lanes.

				Note: This is currently done with the Fietsersbond technology. However, this will be contrasted with the capabilities of the GREENGAGE app
555	Normal	Collect real-time GPS data	539	
554	Normal	Export traffic analysis data	539	
553	Normal	Visualise mobility statistics using different parameters (traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, etc)	539	

Table 14: List of non-functional requirements for North Brabant. IDs are auto-generated.

#	Priority	Subject	Parent issue	Description
857	Low	Usability Requirements	708	The system shall require no more than 15 minutes of training for basic tasks achieve a System Usability Scale (SUS) score above 80 and support intuitive navigation patterns.
856	Low	Integration Requirements	708	The system shall support standard APIs (REST/GraphQL) implement robust error handling for external services and maintain data synchronisation with all integrated platforms.
855	Low	Maintainability Requirements	708	The system shall follow clean code principles implement continuous integration/deployment and maintain comprehensive documentation for all components.
854	Low	Scalability Requirements	708	The system shall support automatic scaling to handle up to 500% increase in user base maintain performance with up to 10TB of mobility data and support regional expansion.
853	Low	Reliability Requirements	708	The system shall maintain 99.9% uptime during peak hours implement automated backups and provide disaster recovery with a Recovery Time Objective (RTO) of 4 hours.
852	Low	Accessibility Requirements	708	The system shall comply with WCAG 2.1 Level AA support multiple languages and provide adaptive interfaces for users with different abilities.
851	Low	Security Requirements	708	The system shall implement GDPR-compliant data protection measures including end-to-end encryption role-based access control and secure authentication with two-factor authentication support.
850	Low	Performance Requirements	708	The system shall maintain response times under 2 seconds for 95% of requests handle at least 1000 concurrent users and process GPS data updates within 5 seconds of receipt.

735	Normal	Security and Privacy	539	The system shall employ strong data encryption, access controls, and adhere to data protection regulations.
734	Normal	Usability	539	Data collection tools (apps, surveys) shall be easy to use and accessible to diverse citizen participants, including those with differing technology skills.
733	Normal	Performance and Scalability	539	The system shall maintain responsiveness and handle increasing amounts of data and users as the project expands.
574	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should meet legal or regulatory requirements, such as GDPR or accessibility standards.		Compliance is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools comply with legal and regulatory requirements, such as GDPR or accessibility standards. The tools should be designed and implemented with compliance in mind, and they should be regularly audited and tested to ensure that they remains compliant.
573	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be easy to maintain, with clear documentation, modular code, and easy-to-understand architecture.		Maintainability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can be easily maintained and updated over time. The tools should have clear documentation, modular code, and an easy-to-understand architecture that allows developers to make changes and updates without introducing errors or breaking the system.
572	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be compatible with other systems, software, or hardware that they may need to interact with.		Compatibility is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can interact and work seamlessly with other systems, software, or hardware that they may need to interact with. The tools should be able to share data and communicate with other systems using standard protocols and formats.
571	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be user-friendly, with a clear and intuitive interface that is easy to use and understand by citizens observers.		Usability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools are easy to use and understand for users. The tools should have a clear and intuitive interface that is easy to navigate and use, even for non-technical users such as citizens observers. They should also be accessible to users with disabilities.
570	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should have appropriate levels of security measures in place to protect against unauthorized access, data breaches, or other security		Security is a critical non-functional requirement that ensures that the software system is protected against unauthorized access, data breaches, and other security threats. The system should have appropriate security measures in place to prevent attacks, and it should comply with relevant privacy and data protection laws and regulations, such as GDPR.

		threats. Privacy and GDPR compliance is essential.		
569	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be able to handle increasing amounts of data, users, and traffic without impacting performance or reliability.		Scalability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can handle increasing amounts of data, users, or traffic without degrading performance or reliability. The tools should be able to scale up or down as needed, and they should be able to accommodate future growth without requiring major changes or upgrades.
568	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be available for use for a reasonable percentage of time and have a reasonable level of uptime, and should be able to recover from failures without losing data.		Reliability is another important non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools are available for use when needed. The tools must be able to operate continuously and reliably without downtime, and they should be able to recover from failures without losing any data.
567	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be able to handle a reasonable number of concurrent users, process a certain number of transactions per second, or respond to user requests within a reasonable time limit.		Performance is a crucial non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can handle the workload the workload that they are designed to handle. The tools must be able to respond to user requests quickly and efficiently without slowing down or crashing.

Table 15: List of functional requirements for Gerace. The IDs are auto-generated.

IDs	Priority	Subject	Parent issue	Description
563	Normal	Provide cross-cutting insights and analyses from various data sources		GREENGAGE tools should provide insights based on the analysis of different data sources to support dialogue between citizens. Please refer to attached image.
583	Normal	Visualise air quality across the city	538	GREENGAGE tools should display comprehensive air quality data across different city locations using interactive maps and visual representations to help citizens understand pollution levels in their areas.

586	Normal	Visualise change of air quality at different times of the day	538	GREENGAGE tools should generate temporal visualisations showing how air quality parameters fluctuate throughout the day, enabling citizens to identify patterns and peak pollution periods.
588	Normal	Export air quality data in standard formats (csv, json, etc)	538	GREENGAGE tools should enable users to export collected air quality data in multiple standard file formats including CSV and JSON, ensuring compatibility with other analysis tools and platforms.
591	Normal	Import air quality data in different formats (csv, json, etc)	538	GREENGAGE tools should support importing air quality data from various file formats including CSV and JSON, allowing integration of data from multiple sources and sensors.
600	Normal	Visualise mobility statistics using different parameters (traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, etc)	581	GREENGAGE tools should create dynamic visualisations of mobility patterns using multiple parameters to help citizens understand traffic conditions, congestion levels and road utilisation across the city.
615	Normal	Collect environment data from portable sensors	538	GREENGAGE tools should interface with mobile environmental sensors to gather real-time data about various environmental parameters, ensuring broad coverage of the urban area.
616	Normal	Visualise environment data (noise levels, waste, water quality, etc)	538	GREENGAGE tools should present environmental measurements including noise pollution, waste management metrics and water quality indicators through intuitive visual displays that citizens can easily interpret.
620	Normal	Collect real-time GPS data	581	GREENGAGE tools should gather continuous GPS location data from compatible devices to enable accurate tracking and analysis of movement patterns within the city.
663	Normal	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering near shops or other amenities)	581	GREENGAGE tools should monitor and record patterns of pedestrian activity and gathering around urban amenities to help understand public space utilisation and inform urban planning decisions.
827	Normal	Allow access to citizens' own data through interactive visualisation	538	Citizens should be able to see what air quality data they have collected and this should be available through different interactive visual projections (e.g., maps, graphs etc).
829	Normal	Compare sensor data with air quality authoritative data	538	Data collected by citizens should be compared with local/national air quality agencies data. In particular trends should be the main point of comparison.

830	Normal	Integration of Copernicus data with collected Air Quality data	538	Identify relevant Copernicus data for air quality monitoring and integrate it with real-time sensor data into visualizations to enhance understanding and decision-making.
832	Normal	Analyse roads status	581	Analyze images to assess road conditions and determine if maintenance is needed. The analysis should identify potholes, illegal dumping, and overgrown vegetation on the road, etc. This will help evaluate the quality of the streets, which may prevent access to different areas or prevent the use of public transport due to poor road conditions.
833	Normal	Detect water pooling on the road sides	581	Identify areas of high accumulation of water in road sections that do not drain properly to better understand areas that require further maintenance and might prevent people from using such roads.
834	Normal	Detect flying tipping and road debris	581	Illegal dumping and road debris can obstruct citizens from using certain roads or accessing specific town areas. This requirement aims to assess whether these roads need maintenance or other interventions.
837	Normal	Identify road signage issues	581	Identify road signage issues such as damaged or missing signs, faded road markings, poor signage visibility, and road signs obscured by vegetation like overgrown plants or trees. Additionally, look for inadequate signage at junctions and side roads, as well as the deterioration of painted stripes and signals on the asphalt. These problems can make roads unsafe, necessitating additional maintenance and interventions.
838	Normal	Analyse municipality CCTV cameras to investigate traffic dynamics	581	The Municipality of Gerace manages a video camera at the entrance of the city for monitoring the ZTL (Restricted Traffic Zone). If this data source can be analysed, the objective would be to understand the flow of vehicles entering and exiting the city based on time periods and schedules, as well as the types of vehicles (e.g., large or small vehicles, bicycles). This data could provide valuable insights, helping to correlate vehicle patterns with road usage and wear, and offering a more comprehensive understanding of traffic dynamics in the area.

Table 16: List of non-functional requirements for Gerace. IDs are auto-generated.

#	Priority	Subject	Parent issue	Description
567	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be able to handle a reasonable number of concurrent users, process a certain number of transactions per second, or		Performance is a crucial non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can handle the workload the workload that they are designed to handle. The tools must be able to respond to user requests quickly and efficiently without slowing down or crashing.

		respond to user requests within a reasonable time limit.		
568	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be available for use for a reasonable percentage of time and have a reasonable level of uptime, and should be able to recover from failures without losing data.		Reliability is another important non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools are available for use when needed. The tools must be able to operate continuously and reliably without downtime, and they should be able to recover from failures without losing any data.
569	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be able to handle increasing amounts of data, users, and traffic without impacting performance or reliability.		Scalability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can handle increasing amounts of data, users, or traffic without degrading performance or reliability. The tools should be able to scale up or down as needed, and they should be able to accommodate future growth without requiring major changes or upgrades.
570	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should have appropriate levels of security measures in place to protect against unauthorized access, data breaches, or other security threats. Privacy and GDPR compliance is essential.		Security is a critical non-functional requirement that ensures that the software system is protected against unauthorized access, data breaches, and other security threats. The system should have appropriate security measures in place to prevent attacks, and it should comply with relevant privacy and data protection laws and regulations, such as GDPR.
571	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be user-friendly, with a clear and intuitive interface that is easy to use and understand by citizens observers.		Usability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools are easy to use and understand for users. The tools should have a clear and intuitive interface that is easy to navigate and use, even for non-technical users such as citizens observers. They should also be accessible to users with disabilities.
572	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be compatible with other systems, software, or hardware that they may need to interact with.		Compatibility is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can interact and work seamlessly with other systems, software, or hardware that they may need to interact with. The tools should be able to share data and communicate with other systems using standard protocols and formats.
573	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be easy to maintain, with clear		Maintainability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can be easily maintained and updated over time. The tools should have clear documentation, modular

		documentation, modular code, and easy-to-understand architecture.		code, and an easy-to-understand architecture that allows developers to make changes and updates without introducing errors or breaking the system.
574	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should meet legal or regulatory requirements, such as GDPR or accessibility standards.		Compliance is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools comply with legal and regulatory requirements, such as GDPR or accessibility standards. The tools should be designed and implemented with compliance in mind, and they should be regularly audited and tested to ensure that they remains compliant.
825	Normal	User interface / visualisation of results are easy to interpret by end users/citizens	538	It is important that citizens should be able to clearly interpret results e.g., graph labelling is clear and understandable, context sensitive help to understand results e.g., Air Quality Index explained, even summary such as whether AQ on a specific point is bad or good, etc.
826	Normal	Where appropriate, allow users to interact with the results through visual interface	538	Users should be able to filter results on selected features, e.g., day, month, year, pollutants, values at a selected point on map and see timeseries data etc.
828	Normal	Ensure data privacy/protection is fully implemented	538	Compliance to ethics protocols and GDPR/other relevant privacy and data protection regulations should be implemented properly
835	Normal	Ensure data privacy/protection is fully implemented	581	Compliance to ethics protocols and GDPR/other relevant privacy and data protection regulations should be implemented properly
836	Normal	User interface / visualisation of results are easy to interpret by end users/citizens	581	It is important that citizens should be able to clearly interpret results e.g., graph labelling is clear and understandable, context sensitive help to understand results.

Table 17: List of functional requirements for Turano. IDs are auto-generated.

IDs	Priority	Subject	Parent issue	Description
551	Normal	Import historical mobility data	578	Enable the import of historical mobility data into the system for analysis and visualization purposes.

563	Normal	Provide cross-cutting insights and analyses from various data sources		GREENGAGE tools should provide insights based on the analysis of different data sources to support dialogue between citizens. Please refer to attached image.
604	Normal	Visualise mobility statistics using different parameters (traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, etc)	578	
608	Normal	Export traffic analysis data	578	
624	Normal	Collect real-time GPS data	578	
635	Normal	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering near shops or other amenities)	578	
872	Normal	Visualise air quality across the city	754	
873	Normal	Visualise change of air quality at different times of the day	754	
874	Normal	Export air quality data in standard formats (csv, json, etc)	754	
875	Normal	Import air quality data in different formats (csv, json, etc)	754	
876	Normal	Collect environment data from portable sensors	754	
877	Normal	Visualise environment data (noise levels, waste, water quality, etc)	754	
880	Normal	Allow access to citizens' own data through interactive visualisation	754	Citizens should be able to see what air quality data they have collected and this should be available through different interactive visual projections (e.g., maps, graphs etc).

882	Normal	Compare sensor data with air quality authoritative data	754	Data collected by citizens should be compared with local/national air quality agencies data. In particular trends should be the main point of comparison.
883	Normal	Integration of Copernicus data with collected Air Quality data	754	Identify relevant Copernicus data for air quality monitoring and integrate it with real-time sensor data into visualizations to enhance understanding and decision-making.
884	Normal	Identify unusual air quality patterns	754	Detect unusual patterns in air quality data, and enable citizens to provide insights via the GREENGAGE app. Citizens can suggest different interpretations, offering deeper understanding of why air quality values fluctuate. Acting as a data diary or retrospective prompt, the app can trigger questions to data collectors when specific values are detected, asking for additional context.
885	Normal	Visualise mobility statistics using different parameters (traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, etc)	580	
886	Normal	Collect real-time GPS data	580	
887	Normal	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering near shops or other amenities)	580	
888	Normal	Analyse roads status	580	Analyze images to assess road conditions and determine if maintenance is needed. The analysis should identify potholes, illegal dumping, and overgrown vegetation on the road, etc. This will help evaluate the quality of the streets, which may prevent access to different areas or prevent the use of public transport due to poor road conditions.
889	Normal	Detect water pooling on the road sides	580	Identify areas of high accumulation of water in road sections that do not drain properly to better understand areas that require further maintenance and might prevent people from using such roads.
890	Normal	Detect flying tipping and road debris	580	Illegal dumping and road debris can obstruct citizens from using certain roads or accessing specific town areas. This requirement aims to assess whether these roads need maintenance or other interventions.
893	Normal	Identify road signage issues	580	Identify road signage issues such as damaged or missing signs, faded road markings, poor signage visibility, and road signs obscured by vegetation like overgrown plants or trees. Additionally, look for inadequate signage at junctions and side roads, as well as the deterioration

				of painted stripes and signals on the asphalt. These problems can make roads unsafe, necessitating additional maintenance and interventions.
894	Normal	Analyse municipality CCTV cameras to investigate traffic dynamics	580	The Municipality of Gerace manages a videocamera at the entrance of the city for monitoring the ZTL (Restricted Traffic Zone). If this data source can be analysed, the objective would be to understand the flow of vehicles entering and exiting the city based on time periods and schedules, as well as the types of vehicles (e.g., large or small vehicles, bicycles). This data could provide valuable insights, helping to correlate vehicle patterns with road usage and wear, and offering a more comprehensive understanding of traffic dynamics in the area.

Table 18: List of non-functional requirements for Turano. IDs are auto-generated.

IDs	Priority	Subject	Parent issue	Description
567	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be able to handle a reasonable number of concurrent users, process a certain number of transactions per second, or respond to user requests within a reasonable time limit.		Performance is a crucial non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can handle the workload the workload that they are designed to handle. The tools must be able to respond to user requests quickly and efficiently without slowing down or crashing.
568	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be available for use for a reasonable percentage of time and have a reasonable level of uptime, and should be able to recover from failures without losing data.		Reliability is another important non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools are available for use when needed. The tools must be able to operate continuously and reliably without downtime, and they should be able to recover from failures without losing any data.
569	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be able to handle increasing amounts of data, users, and traffic without impacting performance or reliability.		Scalability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can handle increasing amounts of data, users, or traffic without degrading performance or reliability. The tools should be able to scale up or down as needed, and they should be able to accommodate future growth without requiring major changes or upgrades.
570	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should have appropriate levels of		Security is a critical non-functional requirement that ensures that the software system is protected against unauthorized access, data breaches, and other security threats. The system

		security measures in place to protect against unauthorized access, data breaches, or other security threats. Privacy and GDPR compliance is essential.		should have appropriate security measures in place to prevent attacks, and it should comply with relevant privacy and data protection laws and regulations, such as GDPR.
571	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be user-friendly, with a clear and intuitive interface that is easy to use and understand by citizens observers.		Usability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools are easy to use and understand for users. The tools should have a clear and intuitive interface that is easy to navigate and use, even for non-technical users such as citizens observers. They should also be accessible to users with disabilities.
572	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be compatible with other systems, software, or hardware that they may need to interact with.		Compatibility is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can interact and work seamlessly with other systems, software, or hardware that they may need to interact with. The tools should be able to share data and communicate with other systems using standard protocols and formats.
573	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should be easy to maintain, with clear documentation, modular code, and easy-to-understand architecture.		Maintainability is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools can be easily maintained and updated over time. The tools should have clear documentation, modular code, and an easy-to-understand architecture that allows developers to make changes and updates without introducing errors or breaking the system.
574	Normal	The GREENGAGE tools should meet legal or regulatory requirements, such as GDPR or accessibility standards.		Compliance is a non-functional requirement that ensures that the GREENGAGE tools comply with legal and regulatory requirements, such as GDPR or accessibility standards. The tools should be designed and implemented with compliance in mind, and they should be regularly audited and tested to ensure that they remains compliant.
878	Normal	User interface / visualisation of results are easy to interpret by end users/citizens	754	It is important that citizens should be able to clearly interpret results e.g., graph labelling is clear and understandable, context sensitive help to understand results e.g., Air Quality Index explained, even summary such as whether AQ on a specific point is bad or good, etc.
879	Normal	Where appropriate, allow users to interact with the results through visual interface	754	Users should be able to filter results on selected features, e.g., day, month, year, pollutants, values at a selected point on map and see timeseries data etc.
881	Normal	Ensure data privacy/protection is fully implemented	754	Compliance to ethics protocols and GDPR/other relevant privacy and data protection regulations should be implemented properly

891	Normal	Ensure data privacy/protection is fully implemented	580	Compliance to ethics protocols and GDPR/other relevant privacy and data protection regulations should be implemented properly
892	Normal	User interface / visualisation of results are easy to interpret by end users/citizens	580	It is important that citizens should be able to clearly interpret results e.g., graph labelling is clear and understandable, context sensitive help to understand results.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

7 Innovation Pilot Development and Next steps

This document presents the finalised innovation pilot specifications, associated use cases and requirements for the GREENGAGE project. The pilot specifications address the European Green Deal objectives according to various local planning strategies with emphasis on sustainable mobility, climate change, mitigation and adaptation co-benefits, and the deployment of green and blue infrastructures to support healthy communities. Accordingly, several common use cases and requirements can be identified that address the needs of the majority of innovation pilots creating scope for common cross-cutting city and regional planning solutions, offering the prospect of wider replicability to cities throughout Europe.

The use cases and requirements have been meticulously co-created with innovation pilots. Final feasibility analysis with technical partners is underway and will be covered in deliverable D2.7. The question that yet remains to be answered is whether the now-finalised requirements and use cases will be addressed within the GREENGAGE project, and if so to what extent. These questions will be answered in D2.7 and the next steps for the project will also be outlined in it.

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